

Natural Killer Cell
Symposium 2021

June 14th - 16th, 2021

Abstract Book

Natural Killer Cell Symposium 2021

nk-symposium.org

Welcome

NATURAL KILLER CELL SYMPOSIUM
BERLIN, GERMANY
JUNE 14TH-16TH 2021

Dear friends and colleagues,

After having postponed the Natural Killer Cell Symposium last year due to the Corona pandemic, we are happy to welcome you to our current virtual meeting!

We thank all the invited speakers for confirming their participation and sharing their results and concepts with us.

We have designed the program to cover all aspects of NK cell biology, from basic to translational research and to encourage interaction within the online format, with short talk instead of posters, and sessions where you can meet the speakers of the day.

We hope you will enjoy the meeting and we look forward to seeing you again soon in person!

Yours,

Chiara Romagnani, Marina Babic, Andreas Diefenbach and Georg Gasteiger

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Program

Monday 14th June 2021

12.45	Young Academy "Meet and Greet", separate zoom meeting, registration needed 12:45- 13:00: Introduction of the YI representatives, Introduction work of Young Immunologists 13:00- 13:40: Maren Büttner: Computational challenges in single-cell profiling	
13.45	Assembly of the DGfl Working Group "NK Cells", Breakout Room 1	
14.15	Opening of the NK2021, Chiara Romagnani and Andreas Diefenbach	
14.25-15.00	Session I: NK Cell Receptors and Development <i>Chair: Roland Jacobs</i>	
14.25	Karl-Johan Malmberg: Adaptive reprogramming of iPSC-derived NK cells	
14.50	Pia Fittje: Impact of HIV-1-mediated downregulation of CD155 on recognition by KIR2DL5+ NK cells	
15.00-16.00	Session II: Adaptive NK Cells <i>Chair: Marcus Altfeld</i>	
15.00	Joseph Sun: Deconvoluting global cytokine signaling networks in NK cells	
15.25	Timo Rückert: Cytomegalovirus induces stable oligoclonal expansions of epigenetically remodeled adaptive NK cells	
15.35	Sophie Flommersfeld: Adaptive-like NK cell responses are composed of conventional and ILC1-like lineages	
15.45	Break	
16.00-17.00	Short Talk Session I + II	
	Session I: ILCs and NK cells in Tissue <i>Chair: Veit Buchholz</i> Breakout Room 1, p101-107	Session II: NK Cell Functions I <i>Chair: Ana Stojanovic</i> Breakout Room 2, p108-114
17.00-18.00	Session III: Circulating and Tissue ILC1 and NK Cells <i>Chair: Georg Gasteiger</i>	
17.00	Marco Colonna: Multi-tissue Single-Cell Analysis Deconstructs the Complexities of Mouse NK-ILC1 Programs in Tissues and Circulation	
17.25	Christin Friedrich: Effector differentiation downstream of lineage commitment in ILC1 is driven by Hobit	
17.35	Ryland Mortlock: Tissue Trafficking Kinetics of Rhesus Macaque Natural Killer Cells Measured by Serial Intravascular Staining	
17.45	Break	
18.00-18.45	Meet the Speaker	
	Breakout Room 1 Kalle Malmberg	Breakout Room 2 Joe Sun
		Breakout Room 3 Marco Colonna

Tuesday, 15th June 2021

12.45-14.00	Industry Symposium, Breakout Room 1			
12.45	Graeme Milton (StemCell Technologies): Tools for NK cell research			
13.00	Cam Loan Tran (Biolegend): Proteogenomics and TotalSeq™ Reagents: A New Era of Single-Cell Analysis			
13.30	Sebastian Lunemann (Cytex Biosciences): Full Spectrum NK Cells; Sarah Metzler: Detection of memory like ILC1s during repeated liver damage by multi parametric flow cytometry; Tommaso Torcellan: Modulation of tissue-niches of resident NK cells and ILC1s in response to infection			
14.15-15.00	Session IV: NK Cell Functions <i>Chair: Carsten Watzl</i>			
14.15	Thierry Walzer: Proteomic changes in NK cells during tumor-induced functional exhaustion			
14.40	Tiphaine Camarasa: NK cell memory to Streptococcus pneumoniae infection			
14.50	Christopher Groth: Dissecting NK cell reactivity against hepatitis B/D virus infection			
15.00-16.00	Session V: NK Cell Subsets and Differentiation <i>Chair: Chiara Romagnani</i>			
15.00	Cynthia Dunbar: Clonal analyses of tissue resident NK cells			
15.25	Dang Nghiem Vo: Defining human NK cell developmental pathway through in vitro NK cell-differentiation map and cellular barcode-tracing			
15.35	Sigrid Wahlen: The transcription factor RUNX2 promotes development of human tissue-resident NK cells			
15.45	Break			
16.00-17.00	Short Talk Session III + IV			
	Session III: NK Cells and Cancer I <i>Chair: Jan P. Böttcher</i> Breakout Room 1, p115-121		Session IV: NK Cell Functions II <i>Chair: Madeleine Bunders</i> Breakout Room 2, p122-128	
17.00-18.00	Session VI: NK Cells and ILCs in Homeostasis, Infection and Inflammation <i>Chair: Andreas Diefenbach</i>			
17.00	Jenny Mjösberg: Innate lymphoid cell (ILC)-differentiation and effector functions relative to T cells in inflammatory bowel disease			
17.25	Donna Farber: Tissue compartmentalization of NK cells and anti-viral immunity			
17.50	Ee von Woon: The unique properties of endometrial NK cells in preparation for pregnancy			
18.00-18.45	Meet the Speaker			
	Breakout Room 1 Thierry Walzer	Breakout Room 2 Cynthia Dunbar	Breakout Room 3 Jenny Mjösberg	Breakout Room 4 Donna Farber
				Breakout Room 5 Todd Fehniger

Wednesday 16th June 2021

11.45-13.00	Industry Symposium: Breakout Room 1	
11.45	Jan Spanholtz (Glycostem Therapeutics): "From bench to bedside and towards product registration - Cord blood stem cell derived NK cells and genetically modified NK cell products for treatment of hematological and solid cancers"	
12.15	Julia Hengst (Miltenyi Biotec): Tools for translational NK cell research	
12.30	Amir Horowitz (Fluidigm sponsored): HLA-E and NKG2A define a novel immune checkpoint axis in bladder cancer	
13.00-13.45	Meet the Speaker	
	Breakout Room 1 Bojan Polic	Breakout Room 2 Ashley Moffett
		Breakout Room 3 Eric Vivier
13.45	<i>Break</i>	
14.00-15.00	Session VII: NK Cells and Metabolism <i>Chair: Markus Uhrberg</i>	
14.00	Bojan Polic: The role of NKG2D in development of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis and liver fibrosis	
14.25	Lea Boller: Effect of glucose-transporter inhibitors on the function of Natural Killer cells	
14.35	Elisabeth Littwitz-Salomon: Metabolic requirements of NK cells during the response against retroviral infection	
14.45	<i>Break</i>	
14.50-15.15	Session VIII: Uterine NK Cells <i>Chair: Carmen Infante-Duarte</i>	
14.50-15.15	Ashley Moffett: NK cells and Human Reproduction	
15.15-15.45	Session IX: NK Cells in SARS-CoV-2 <i>Chair: Lutz Walter</i>	
15.15	Mario Witkowski: Untimely TGF- β responses in severe COVID-19 inhibit NK cell function and NK cell-mediated control of SARS-CoV-2 replication	
15.25	Benjamin Krämer: Persistent natural killer cell dysfunction in severe COVID-19	
15.35	Quirin Hammer: SARS-CoV-2-derived peptides regulate NK cell responses through HLA-E	
15.45	<i>Break</i>	
16.00-17.00	Short Talk Session V + VI	
	Session V: NK Cells and Cancer II <i>Chair: Gabriela Wiedemann</i> Breakout Room 1, p129-135	Session VI: NK and ILC Development and Regulation <i>Chair: Marina Babic</i> Breakout Room 2, p136-143

17.00-18.00	Session X: NK Cells and Cancer Immunotherapy <i>Chair: Evelyn Ulrich</i>
17.00	Eric Vivier: Harnessing innate immunity in cancer therapies: the example of Natural Killer Cell Engagers
17.25	Anna-Marie Pedde: A dysfunctional program imprinted by PGE2 signaling shuts off NK cell communication pathways and disables immunosurveillance of metastasis
17.35	Todd Fehniger: Translating NK cell memory as cancer immunotherapy
18.00-19.00	Round Table: NK Cells and Cellular Therapy <i>Moderator: Heidi Cerwenka</i> Todd Fehniger, Ulrike Köhl, Kalle Malmberg, Eric Vivier
19.00	Closing Remarks and best selected talk award Marina Babic, Chiara Romagnani, Andreas Diefenbach, Georg Gasteiger

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Short Talks

Session I: ILCs and NK Cells in Tissues

Monday, June 14th, 2021, 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 1**

Chair: Veit Buchholz

101.	Chuanfeng Wu: Tissue-Resident Clonal Expansions of Rhesus Macaque NK Cells
102.	Tommaso Torcellan: Modulation of tissue-niches of resident NK cells and ILC1s in response to infection
103.	Antonia O. Cuff: The role of IL-22 and IL-22 producing immune cells in the uterus
104.	Kim M. Kaiser: Increased frequency of IL-17A producing ILC3 in duodenal mucosa in familial adenomatous polyposis
105.	Sarah Metzler: Memory like ILC1s during repeated liver damage
106.	Silvina Romero-Suárez: The Aryl-hydrocarbon Receptor-dependent Regulation of Innate Lymphoid Cell Responses in Skin Inflammation
107.	Jia-Xiang See: Innate Lymphocytes Regulate Immune Functions of Liver Sinusoidal Endothelial Cells

Session II: NK Cell Functions I

Monday, June 14th, 2021, 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 2**

Chair: Ana Stojanovic

108.	Jenny F. Kühne: Donor lymphocytes in peripheral blood of patients after lung transplantation comprise high frequencies of KIR-positive T and NK cell subsets
109.	Greta Meyer: Influence of HCMV variants expressing NKG2D ligands on immune cell activation
110.	Annika Niehrs: Liver organoids as a model system to study immune cell recognition of HBV-infected hepatocytes
111.	Kerri Hagemann: Natural Killer cell-mediated ADCC in SARS-CoV-2-infected individuals and vaccine recipients
112.	Leonore Mensching: Priming of NK cell effector function by macrophages in HIV-1 infection
113.	Maria Carolina Accioly Brelaz-de-Castro: Expression of NKG2D by NK and NKT cells by cutaneous leishmaniasis patients before and after treatment
114.	Lea Boller: Engagement of CD56 can stimulate Natural Killer cell responses

Session III: NK Cells and Cancer I

Tuesday, June 15th, 2021, 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 1**

Chair: Jan P. Böttcher

115.	Nina Lamers-Kok: Enhancing functionality of NK cells towards colorectal cancer cell lines
116.	Upasana Sunil Arvindam: Oxygen concentration significantly alters NK cell phenotype and function: implications for immunotherapy within the solid tumor microenvironment
117.	Monica Raimo: Identification of specific gene expression regulation during activation and cancer cell killing of oNKord® Natural Killer cells by transcriptome analysis and comparison with cytotoxic potential
118.	Irene Mattioli: The macrophage tetraspan MS4A4A enhances Dectin-1-dependent NK cell-mediated resistance to metastasis
119.	Philippa Meiser: The role of cDC1/NK cell communication within the tumor microenvironment for anti-cancer immunity
120.	Eimear Mylod: Exploring the role of fractalkine (CX3CL1) in natural killer cell cell chemotaxis and phenotype in obesity associated cancers
121.	Brwa Hussein: Impact of NKC locus gene polymorphisms on natural killer cell function and outcome of immunotherapy in acute myeloid leukemia

Session IV: ILCs and NK Cells Functions IITuesday, June 15th, 2021. 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 2***Chair: Madeleine Bunders*

122.	Andrew Hogan: Investigating the metabolic requirements of cytokine induced natural killer cell training & the impact of obesity
123.	Oscar Fabian Garcia Aponte: Metabolic Differences on NK-92 cells expressing distinctive cytotoxic profiles from varying culturing process parameters
124.	Vivian Bönemann: The Role of Granzymes in NK Cell Cytotoxicity
125.	Marta Freitas Monteiro: Characterization of a panel of immortalized Natural Killer cell lines expressing allelic variants for FCGR3A
126.	Simone Mantesso: Improving NK cell effector functions and manufacturing by EOMES and T-bet overexpression
127.	Gaitan Fabrice Njiomegnie: Adipokines' function in obesity-induced NK cell dysregulation
128.	Christian Körner: TRAIL Engagement Induces Granule Exocytosis and Facilitates Degranulation of NK Cells Recognizing HIV-infected Target Cells

Session V: NK Cells and Cancer IIWednesday, June 16th, 2021, 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 1***Chair: Gabriela Wiedemann*

129.	Katarina Mirjačić Martinović: Increased circulating TGF- β 1 is associated with impairment in NK cell effector functions in metastatic melanoma patients
130.	Jiri Eitler: PARP inhibitors Olaparib and AG-14361 render otherwise resistant breast and ovarian cancers sensitive towards NK cell mediated killing
131.	Klara Klein: Oncogenic potential of mutant STAT5B in natural killer cells
132.	Amanda van Vliet: Ex vivo expanded NK cells show potent anti-tumour activity against melanoma
133.	Tobias Bexte: Non-viral Sleeping Beauty transposon engineered CD19-CAR-NK cells show a safe genomic integration profile and high antileukemic efficiency
134.	Valentin Picant: Emergence of polyfunctional ST2+ NK cells with antitumor properties following IL-33 activation
135.	Caroline Hennig: Complement 5a Receptor 2 (C5aR2) expression regulates NKp46 levels and influences formation of pulmonary metastases

Session VI: NK and ILC Development and RegulationWednesday, June 16th, 2021, 16.00-17.00, **Breakout Room 2***Chair: Marina Babic*

136.	Daniela C. Hernandez: A comprehensive platform for the faithful generation of human innate lymphoid cell lineages from CD34+ hematopoietic progenitors
137.	Diana Schnoegl: Regulation of Fra-2 is essential for correct Natural Killer Cell development and function
138.	Sabrina Bianca Bennstein: Deep characterisation of neonatal innate lymphoid subsets reveals a unique precursor able to generate NKG2A-KIR+ NK cells
139.	Laura Kiekens: T-BET and EOMES accelerate and enhance functional differentiation of human nk cells by programming HPCs
140.	Jan Raabe: KLRG1+ILCp as a Putative Progenitor of IL-13-Producing ILC3 in the Human Liver
141.	Minoru Kanaya: Toggling of NKG2A expression drives adaptive reprogramming and functional specialization of iPSC-derived CD19 CAR NK cells
142.	Marek Jedlicka: Ex vivo Expanded NK Cells and Their Immunometabolism
143.	Ameera Gaafar: Forecast the outcome of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation via the evaluation of NK cells functions and their differential expression of natural killer cells receptors in the donors

Sponsors

We thank the following companies and institutions for supporting the Natural Killer Cell Symposium 2021:

Abstracts

1 INVITED TALK

Adaptive reprogramming of iPSC-derived NK cells

Kalle Malmberg

Cancer Immunology, The University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway. k.j.malmberg@medisin.uio.no

Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived natural killer (iPSC-NK) cells offer a promising platform for off-the-shelf cell therapy against cancer. iPSCs can be routinely generated from a variety of easily obtainable sources such as skin and peripheral blood. Once reprogrammed, iPSCs are able to undergo essentially unlimited expansion *in vitro* without losing pluripotency. Therefore, iPSCs can serve as a resource to produce unlimited numbers of NK cells for cell therapy. Moreover, iPSC-NK cells can be used as a platform for genetic engineering to improve specificity, persistence, tumor cell homing and functionality of the final cell product. These functional edits are superimposed on the innate reactivity of NK cells to stress ligands and MHC downregulation.

In this talk, I will briefly review the genetic regulatory circuits involved in NK cell differentiation and provide molecular evidence for a temporal relationship between common NK cell subsets, including the transition from CD56bright NK cells to CD56dim NK cells. The detailed transcriptional map of human NK cell differentiation forms a basis to decipher maturation, repertoire diversity and education of iPSC-NK cells. Specifically, our results point to a crucial role for HLA-E independent NKG2A-driven acquisition of a mature effector cell phenotype.

Intriguingly, CRISPR-mediated deletion of NKG2A in CAR19-iPSC-NK cells led to adaptive reprogramming with a switch to expression of the activating receptor NKG2C associated with enhanced IFN- γ production in response to targets expressing supraphysiological levels of HLA-E.

Acquisition of KIR occurred gradually during iPSC-NK cell differentiation and was associated with higher expression of Eomes and granzyme B as well as increased functionality. Reprogramming of terminally differentiated single KIR expressing CD8 T cells into iPSC-NK cells lead to a complete resetting of the KIR repertoire, involving methylation of the promoter region. The emerging KIR repertoires from a single iPSC clone were stochastic between runs but fixed in individual experiments, approaching the original KIR repertoire in the donor over multiple runs.

Although signaling through KIR and NKG2A receptors was attenuated in iPSC-NK cells compared to PB-NK cells, the degree of inhibition varied with the level of expression of the cognate ligands highlighting the need to consider inhibitory receptor-repertoire diversity in clonal iPSC-NK cell therapy products.

2 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Impact of HIV-1-mediated downregulation of CD155 on recognition by KIR2DL5+ NK cells

Pia Fittje¹, Angelique Hölzemer^{1,2}, Wilfredo B. Garcia^{1,3}, Annika Niehrs¹, Sarah Vollmers¹, Gloria Martus¹, Daniel Sauter⁴, Marcus Altfeld¹

¹Leibniz Institute for Experimental Virology (HPI), Hamburg, Germany; ²Department of Internal Medicine, University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany; ³Department of Pathology, Massachusetts General Hospital/Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA; ⁴Institute for Medical Virology and Epidemiology of Viral Diseases, University Hospital Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany. pia.fittje@leibniz-hpi.de

Introduction: Ligands for the inhibitory NK cell receptor KIR2DL5 are not well defined. The Poliovirus receptor (PVR, CD155) has recently been shown to not only bind the activating receptor DNAM1, but to also interact with KIR2DL5. Nevertheless, the functional relevance of KIR2DL5/CD155 interactions for NK cells

is unknown. Previous studies have suggested that HIV-1 decreases CD155-expression on infected cells and thereby evade immune recognition by DNAM1-positive NK cells. However, the newly described interaction between KIR2DL5 and CD155 indicates a more complex regulation of NK cell responses by CD155.

Methods: Binding of KIR2DL5 to CD155 was analyzed using KIR-IgG fusion construct (Fc) staining of CD155-coated beads and KIR2DL5-expressing reporter cells. To study the functional consequences of interactions between CD155 and KIR2DL5, NK cell degranulation in response to CD155-expressing target cells was assessed using primary human NK cells. Degranulation was determined by surface expression of CD107a. To analyze cell surface expression of CD155 during HIV-1 infection, stimulated primary human CD4⁺ T cells were infected with different wild type HIV-1 strains or their respective Δ nef mutants. CD155-expression on infected and uninfected cells was quantified by flow cytometry.

Results: We observed binding of KIR2DL5-Fc constructs to CD155 and activation of KIR2DL5⁺ reporter cells after co-incubation with CD155-coated beads, determined by an upregulation of CD69 on the cell surface. Primary human KIR2DL5⁺ NK cells displayed lower CD107a expression levels after incubation with CD155-expressing

target cells compared to non-PVR expressing target cells, indicating NK cell inhibition mediated by the KIR2DL5-CD155 interaction. NK cell inhibition was abrogated by blocking the interaction between CD155 and KIR2DL5. Furthermore, all tested HIV-1 strains down-modulated CD155 on the surface of infected primary CD4⁺ T cells in a Nef-dependent manner.

Conclusion: CD155 serves as a functional ligand for the inhibitory NK cell receptor KIR2DL5, thereby inhibiting KIR2DL5⁺ NK cell function. CD155-levels are decreased on HIV-1-infected cells by a Nef-dependent mechanism, potentially in an effort to evade DNAM1-mediated recognition by NK cells. However, downregulation of CD155 may result in loss of inhibition of KIR2DL5⁺ NK cells in individuals encoding for KIR2DL5, and might increase the antiviral capacity of KIR2DL5⁺ NK cells during HIV-1 infection.

3 INVITED TALK

Deconvoluting global cytokine signaling networks in NK cells

Joseph Sun

Immunology, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, New York, USA. sunj@mskcc.org

Cytokine signaling via signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) proteins is crucial for optimal antiviral responses of natural killer (NK) cells. However, the pleiotropic effects of both cytokine and STAT signaling preclude the ability to precisely attribute molecular changes to either source. In this study, we employ a multi-“omics” approach to deconstruct and rebuild the complex interaction of several cytokine signaling pathways in NK cells. We uncover a global proinflammatory and homeostatic cytokine cooperative axis, as well as a proinflammatory antagonism toward the

type I IFN axis that is supplemented by this cooperation. We demonstrate distinct STAT modes of epigenetic regulation, and generate a network of STAT targets that highlights an integrated negative feedback loop. Finally, we identify shared signatures between mouse *in vitro* profiles and profiles from viral infection and humans, highlighting clinically translatable targets. Overall, we begin to unravel the intricate crosstalk between cytokine signaling pathways, and offer a valuable resource for improving cellular immunotherapy.

4 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Cytomegalovirus induces stable oligoclonal expansions of epigenetically remodeled adaptive NK cells

Timo Rückert¹, Pawel Durek¹, Frederik Heinrich¹, Caleb A Lareau³, Leif S Ludwig⁴, Mir-Farzin Mashreghi¹, Chiara Romagnani^{1,2}

¹Deutsches Rheuma-Forschungszentrum Berlin, a Leibniz Institute, Berlin, Germany; ²Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Department of Gastroenterology, Infectiology and Rheumatology, Berlin, Germany; ³Cell Circuits and Epigenomics Program, Broad Institute, Cambridge, MA, United States; ⁴Berlin Institute of Health at Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany and Max-Delbrück-Center for Molecular Medicine in the Helmholtz Association (MDC), Berlin; Institute for Medical Systems Biology (BIMSB), Berlin, Germany. timo.rueckert@dfz.de

Infection with Cytomegalovirus (CMV) induces the expansion of transcriptionally and epigenetically remodeled NKG2C⁺ NK cells. Direct interaction of NKG2C with CMV-derived peptides recruits naïve NKG2C⁺ NK cells into the immune response against CMV, triggering effector functions and inducing their proliferation and differentiation. Studies in mice demonstrated that murine adaptive NK cell expansions are oligoclonal, which has also been speculated for human NK cells based on their strict expression of self-MHC-specific KIRs. Prolonged preservation of adaptive NK cells in patients with progressive immunodeficiencies raised questions on their maintenance mechanisms compared to the conventional NK cell pool. By studying the transcriptional and epigenetic landscape of human NK cells from healthy CMV-seropositive and seronegative individuals on the single-cell level, we construct a differentiation model which suggests discontinuous maintenance of adaptive NK cells. While naïve and adaptive NKG2C⁺ NK cells

co-exist in CMV-seropositive individuals, naïve NKG2C⁺ NK cells do not seem to be converted to adaptive cells during steady-state. This concept is further supported by accumulation of specific mutations in mitochondrial DNA of adaptive NK cells, which are maintained for at least 11 months, demonstrating remarkable clonality and stability of the adaptive NK cell pool. Finally, we demonstrate that, akin to memory T cells, the epigenomes of adaptive NK cells show a chromatin accessibility profile with strong enrichment of AP-1 motifs, indicative of a role of this transcription factor family as pioneering factors in chromatin opening after CMV-induced activation. Together, these findings provide insights into the generation and maintenance of adaptive NK cells and strengthen the evidence of overlapping mechanisms of immune memory across cell types.

5 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Adaptive-like NK cell responses are composed of conventional and ILC1-like lineages

Sophie Flommersfeld¹, Jan P. Böttcher², Jonatan Ersching³, Michael Flossdorf¹, Philippa Meiser², Ludwig O. Pachmayr¹, Justin Leube¹, Inge Hensel¹, Sebastian Jarosch¹, Qin Zhang⁴, M. Zeeshan Chaudhry⁵, Immanuel Andrae¹, Matthias Schiemann¹, Dirk H. Busch¹, Luca Cicin-Sain⁵, Joseph C. Sun⁷, Georg Gasteiger⁶, Gabriel D. Victora³, Thomas Höfer⁴, Veit R. Buchholz¹, Simon Grassmann¹

¹Institute for Medical Microbiology, Immunology and Hygiene, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Munich, Germany; ²Institute of Molecular Immunology and Experimental Oncology, Klinikum Rechts der Isar, School of Medicine, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Munich, Germany; ³Laboratory of Lymphocyte Dynamics, The Rockefeller University, New York, NY 10065, USA; ⁴Division of Theoretical Systems Biology, German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), Heidelberg, Germany; ⁵Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research, Braunschweig, Germany; ⁶Würzburg Institute of Systems Immunology; ⁷Immunology Program, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, New York, USA. sophie.flommersfeld@tum.de

Upon viral infection, natural killer (NK) cells expressing certain germline-encoded receptors are selected, expanded and maintained in an adaptive-like manner. Currently, all NK cells participating in such responses are thought to differentiate along a common pathway. However, by mapping the fate of single NK cells upon murine cytomegalovirus infection, we find that these adaptive-like responses originate from two NK cell lineages that maintain distinct clonal identities throughout infection. One of these is equivalent to recirculating conventional NK (cNK) cells while the other shows splenic residency and selectively associates with dendritic cells (DCs). These spleen-resident NK (srNK) cells are transcriptionally similar to type 1 innate lymphocytes (ILC1s) but capable of vigorous clonal expansion and direct recognition of virus infected cells. These features

enable early induction of DC clustering and optimal T cell priming and establish srNK cells as a separate lineage that unites critical features of cNK cells and ILC1s.

6 INVITED TALK

Multi-tissue Single-Cell Analysis Deconstructs the Complexities of Mouse NK-ILC1 Programs in Tissues and Circulation

Adelle P. McFarland¹, Adam Jelinski², Shuang-Yin Wang², Victor S. Cortez¹, Tomer Landsberger², Hannah Miller¹, Biancamaria Ricci¹, Roberta Faccio³, Ido Amit², Marco Colonna¹

¹Department of Pathology and Immunology, Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO, USA; ²Department of Immunology, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot, Israel; ³Department of Orthopedics, Washington University School of Medicine, and Shriners Children's Hospital in St. Louis, St. Louis, MO, USA.
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Natural killer (NK) cells and type 1 innate lymphoid cells (ILC1s) are a heterogeneous group of T-bet⁺ innate cells that produce IFN- γ and are broadly defined as lineage-NK1.1⁺ NKp46⁺ cells in mice. ILC1s definition primarily stems from studies on liver-resident and small intestinal populations. However, ILC1s in many anatomical sites, including adipose tissue, salivary glands, and uterus, exhibit non-uniform programs that do not adequately overlap with those of liver or gut ILC1s or NK cells. In this study, we performed single-cell RNA sequencing on murine NK1.1⁺NKp46⁺ cells from blood, spleen, lymph

nodes, liver, salivary gland, uterus, adipose tissue, small intestines, and solid tumors. By including cells from an array of niches we identified tissue-specific ILC1 subsets, while circulating NK cells were defined by a spectrum of proliferating, effector and migration programs that were reshaped in tumor-bearing mice. This detailed NK-ILC1 molecular atlas advances research on NK-ILC1 and their therapeutic exploitation.

7 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Effector differentiation downstream of lineage commitment in ILC1 is driven by Hobit across tissues

Christin Friedrich¹, Renske Taggenbrock², Rmi Doucet-Ladevze¹, Gosia Golda³, Rebekka Moenius¹, Panagiota Arampatzis⁴, Mercedes Gomez de Agero¹, Wolfgang Kastenmueller¹, Antoine-Emmanuel Saliba⁵, Dominic Grn³, Klaas P. J. M. van Gisbergen², Georg Gasteiger¹

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Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) mediate early immunity against infection and participate in tissue inflammation and homeostasis. It is unclear how ILCs acquire effector function, and whether these mechanisms differ between organs. Through multiplex single-cell mRNA-sequencing we identified markers of early differentiation stages of lineage-committed Tbet⁺ ILC1. These cells were present across different organs and had the potential to generate ILC1 with marked effector function. Differentiating ILC1 forfeited their expansion potential while increasing expression of effector molecules, reminiscent of T cell differentiation in secondary lymphoid organs. The transcription factor Hobit was induced upon lineage-commitment of ILC1s and was required for their effector maturation. These findings reveal sequential mechanisms of ILC1 lineage commitment and ILC1

effector maturation that are conserved across tissues. Our analyses suggest that early Hobit⁺ ILC1 emerge in the periphery and acquire a spectrum of organ-specific effector phenotypes through a uniform Hobit-dependent differentiation pathway driven by local cues.

8 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Tissue Trafficking Kinetics of Rhesus Macaque Natural Killer Cells Measured by Serial Intravascular Staining

Ryland D. Mortlock¹, Chuanfeng Wu¹, E. Lake Potter², David S.J. Allan³, Mario Roederer², Cynthia E. Dunbar¹

¹Translational Stem Cell Biology Branch, National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, NIH, Bethesda, Maryland, USA;

²Vaccine Research Center, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, NIH, Bethesda, Maryland, USA;

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Non-human primate animal models have been utilized to study natural killer (NK) cell biology due to the close phylogenetic relationship between humans and primates. Rhesus macaques (RM) have three distinct subsets of NK cells: CD56+CD16-, CD56-CD16+, and CD56-CD16-. RM CD56+CD16- and CD56-CD16+ resemble human CD56brightCD16- and CD56dimCD16+ NK cells respectively at the receptor and transcriptional level (Hong et al, Front. Immunol. 2013). We investigated tissue trafficking kinetics for the three subsets of RM NK cells using serial intravascular staining (SIVS) (Potter et al, Sci. Transl. Med. 2021).

Animals were given serial infusions of differently colored fluorescent anti-CD45 antibodies at multiple time points up to 48 hours before euthanization. Each infusion labels all leukocytes in the vascular space at that moment in time. Peripheral blood (PB), lymphoid tissues (bone marrow, lymph node [LN] and spleen), and non-lymphoid tissues (liver, lung, and intestines) were collected immediately after euthanization, stained for NK cell markers and quantified for the presence of the various SIVS antibodies.

The three RM NK subsets showed consistent differences in tissue trafficking kinetics. Approximately 80% of CD56-CD16+ NK cells stained positive for all SIVS antibodies given up to 48 hours before, suggesting sustained

residence in the circulation. In contrast, CD56+CD16- NK cells had a markedly shorter residence time in PB, with only 20% positive for the -48 hour SIVS antibody. CD56-CD16- NK cells had an intermediate residence time in PB. Additionally, CD56-CD16+ NK cells had a faster entry rate into LN, with approximately 30% of LN CD56-CD16+ NK cells staining positive for the -2 hour infusion whereas only 3% and 2% of CD56+CD56- and CD56-CD16- respectively stained positive. CD56-CD16- NK cells had the highest proportion of long-term tissue residence in LN, defined as negative for all SIVS antibodies.

Based on our results, CD56+CD16- and CD56-CD16- NK cells are more likely than CD56-CD16+ NK cells to take up residence in tissue, supported by a lower tissue entry rate (and thus lower exit rate, assuming steady state) and shorter residence time in PB. On the other hand, CD56-CD16+ NK have a long residence time in PB and traffic in and out of tissue at a faster rate than other NK cell subsets. Quantifying the kinetic entry rates of NK subsets across an array of tissue paves the way for future studies to measure NK cell trafficking kinetics in response to stimuli such as hematopoietic stem cell transplant, viral infection or contact hypersensitivity.

9 INVITED TALK

Proteomic changes in NK cells during tumor-induced functional exhaustion

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Natural Killer (NK) cells are cytotoxic lymphocytes involved in cancer immunosurveillance. As tumors develop, NK cells often become dysfunctional, and the mechanisms associated with this dysfunction remain poorly understood. To address this question, we

engineered a new mouse model of lymphoma, RMA-KR, strongly immunogenic for NK cells that grows in several organs including the spleen. When injected iv into mice, RMA-KR cells are initially controlled by NK cells in the spleen, in a perforin and IFN γ -dependent manner while

the parental cell line (RMA) is not controlled. However, at later stages, NK cells become dysfunctional which coincides with RMA-KR growth. NK cell dysfunction is very broad, affecting all cytokine and activating receptors pathways. RNAseq and Seahorse analyses show that NK cell dysfunction is not associated with transcriptional or metabolic changes. By contrast, mass spectrometry analyses revealed broad changes in the proteome expressed by dysfunctional NK cells as compared with

control or activated NK cells. In particular, dysfunctional NK cells express lower levels of several activating receptors and key signaling intermediates, and higher levels of proteins involved in immunosuppressive mechanisms. We propose that NK cell dysfunction is a complex phenomenon involving multiple post-transcriptional negative feedback mechanisms.

10 SELECTED SHORT TALK

NK cell memory to *Streptococcus pneumoniae* infection

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The role of natural killer cells (NK) in bacterial infection as both direct antagonist and indirect mediators of immune responses is increasingly documented. Furthermore, the ability of NK cells to display innate immune memory, as characterized by an epigenetic signature giving rise to a stronger response to secondary stimulation, is a promising approach in the fight against infectious diseases. While NK cell memory has been shown in various viral infections, NK cell memory to bacterial infection remain understudied. Using a mouse model of intranasal infection with the Gram-positive bacterium *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, we show that

NK cells acquire memory following sub-lethal infection. Transferred memory NK cells are sufficient to confer protection against lethal infection in a process dependent on IFN γ and epigenetic modifications. Cell markers of virally induced NK cell memory do not characterize bacterially induced memory, however, single-cell sequencing revealed new populations of NK cells in comparison to naïve NK cells. Understanding such NK cell memory adds another facet to NK cell function, and the harnessing of this response could lead to the design of new prophylactic strategies against bacterial infection.

11 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Dissecting NK cell reactivity against hepatitis B/D virus infection

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Viral hepatitis infections are a major health challenge that can contribute to fibrosis, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Viral hepatitis infections can be caused by five different hepatoviruses (HAV, HBV, HCV, HDV, HEV).

Currently, efficient vaccines are available against HAV, HBV and HEV. In recent years, novel drugs targeting viral replication, assembly and secretion of the HCV have been developed and showed impressive results

in eradicating the virus and improve patient outcome. In contrast, no treatment options to directly target the HDV are available. Replication of the HDV depends on the co-infection with the HBV, which provides for the production of the necessary envelope protein. HDV/ HBV co-infections have been shown to lead to a more rapid and severe disease progression compared to HBV mono-infections. Recently, the entry receptor for HBV and HDV, the sodium taurocholate co-transporting

polypeptide (NTCP), has been described, which was the prerequisite for the development of the entry-inhibitor for HDV and HBV, Myrcludex B. Although this compound does not lead to virus eradication, it prevents the spread of the virus in the liver and significantly reduces disease severity. Nevertheless, understanding hepatitis D pathogenesis and the associated immune response is crucial to further improve treatment strategies. Natural killer (NK) cells are important effector cells of the innate immune system that target virus infected cells. Using co-culture systems of NK cells isolated from peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) and HDV-infected

hepatoma cells, we demonstrate profound activation of NK cells in the presence of HDV infected cells. Activation of NK cells was associated with increased expression of interferon (IFN)-gamma, CD69 and increased NK cell degranulation. In addition, HDV infections led to increased abundance of IFN-gamma, IFN-lambda, TNF-alpha, and interleukin (IL)-6 in co-culture supernatants. Using transwell assay approaches and assays with neutralizing antibodies, we will further decipher the exact mechanisms of NK cell activation in HDV infections and validate these in relevant patient cohorts.

12 INVITED TALK

Insights into NK cell life histories and response to CMV infection in the macaque model

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Over a decade of murine and macaque studies as well as human NK cell adoptive transfer and allogeneic transplantation clinical protocol have provided evidence supporting adaptive memory properties of NK cells, particularly in response to herpes virus infection or reactivation, however the mechanisms leading to expansion and persistence of mature adaptive cells with specific reactivity, in the absence of diverse antigen receptor rearrangements, remain unclear.

We have applied genetic barcoding of rhesus macaque hematopoietic cells stem cells to interrogate the landscape of NK cell production, expansion, and life histories at a clonal level long term and following proliferative challenges and primary CMV infection. We previously identified oligoclonal mature CD56⁺CD16⁺ NK expansions waxing, waning or persisting over time in the blood (PB), clonally uncoupled from other hematopoietic lineages, including CD56⁺CD16⁻ NK cells. Specific CD56⁻CD16⁺ expanded clones segregate with surface expression of specific killer immunoglobulin-like receptors (Wu, STM, 2018). Primary CMV infection resulted in marked clonal shifts (Truitt, Front Imm, 2019). Timed administrations of several distinctly-colored antibodies binding to intravascular (IV) leukocytes was utilized to demonstrate prolonged IV retention of CD16⁺ NK, with limited exchange of this compartment with tissue resident lymph node populations, in contrast to T and B cells.

We have now studied clonal characteristics of tissue NK cells, and document oligoclonal NK expansions shared across multiple tissues, distinct from PB CD16⁺ NK expanded clones.

However, these clones can be detected within the circulating NKG2⁺CD56⁻CD16⁻ (DN) compartment, suggesting seeding of tissue-specific clones via this blood population. Together, our results indicate that linear NK cell production from multipotent hematopoietic progenitors or less mature CD56⁺CD16⁻ cells is negligible during homeostasis and moderate proliferative stress. In such settings, peripheral compartmentalized self-renewal can maintain the composition of distinct, differentiated NK cell subpopulations in both the PB and tissues.

We have now explored NK single cell gene expression and coincident cell surface marker expression in response to primary and secondary rhesus CMV infection. Multiple distinct clusters are present, corresponding to subpopulations of CD56⁺CD16⁻, DN and CD56⁻CD16⁺ NK, along with mitotic and inflammatory NK cells. With primary CMV infection, a marked increase in inflammatory and depletion of CD56⁺CD16⁻ clusters occurs, followed by a later increase in a cluster of NK cells with adaptive features. Secondary CMV infection does not result in similar marked shifts in NK characteristics at a single cell level.

13 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Defining human NK cell developmental pathway through *in vitro* NK cell differentiation map and cellular barcode tracing

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Natural Killer (NK) cells hold great potential for anti-cancer immunotherapy due to their unique ability to detect and eliminate malignant cells by direct cytotoxicity and cytokine secretion. Despite recent progress in understanding of human NK cell development, much of this knowledge is derived from *ex vivo* studies of multiple NK cell subsets and precursors isolated from different tissues. This approach does not fully capture developmental trajectories and the dynamics of differentiation pathway from hematopoietic stem/progenitor cells (HSPC) to fully mature functional NK cells. Herein, we established and characterized multiple steps of human NK cell generation and maturation *in vitro* from HSPC, where discrete NK cell developmental stages are followed during a 4-week co-culture on OP9 stroma. Employing diverse markers from early lymphoid to NK-specific receptors associated with lineage identity and maturation, we generated an UMAP-directed NK developmental trajectory that can be divided into 5 discrete stages, based on the proposed linear model of human NK cell development *ex vivo* (Freud et al., *Semin Immunol*, 2014). Differentiation kinetics, transcription factor profile (Tbet, Eomes) and expression of effector molecules (Prf, GrzB) confirmed that *in vitro* NK cell maturation progressed through this developmental trajectory in a sequential manner. Functional assays including IFN γ secretion, degranulation (CD107a) and direct K562 tumor cells

cytotoxicity, supported the increased effector functions as differentiating NK cells progressed from Stage 3 to Stage 5. Interestingly, our UMAP trajectory also revealed two discrete Stage 3 clusters, based on differential CD56 expression as previously reported in human tonsil *ex vivo* (Chen et al., *Immunity* 2018). Further analysis of CD56⁺ Stage 3 population heterogeneity *in vitro* revealed that all ROR γ t⁺ ILC3 cells were found within the CD56⁺NKp44⁺CD94⁻ gate, while the remaining substantial fraction had a ROR γ t-DNAM-1+T-bet⁺ phenotype equivalent to immature Stage 3 NK cells. Therefore our data suggests for additional cell surface markers to efficiently discriminate Stage 3 NK cells from ILC3 cells. Finally, to address the long-standing question whether human NK cell development follows a linear or branched model (Cichocki et al., *Front Immunol*, 2019), we are performing DNA-barcoding tracing experiments to investigate the contribution and developmental relationship between different stages during *in vitro* NK cell differentiation. In summary, we established a structural framework which allows to further dissect human NK cell development *in vitro* and provides a platform for studies on characterizing transcriptional regulatory networks controlling this process.

14 SELECTED SHORT TALK

The transcription factor RUNX2 promotes development of human tissue-resident NK cells

Sigrid Wahlen¹, Filip Matthijssens², Wouter Van Looke², Sylvie Taveirne³, Laura Kiekens¹, Eva Persyn¹, Els van Ammel¹, Zenzi De Vos¹, Filip Van Nieuwerburgh⁴, Tom Taghon¹, Bart Vandekerckhove¹, Pieter Van Vlierberghe², Georges Leclercq¹

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Natural killer (NK) cells are crucial players of the innate immune response against virus infections and cancer, acting as both immune regulators and direct cytotoxic agents. Their development is a complex process that in humans starts from hematopoietic stem cells (HSC) in the bone marrow and ends in the peripheral blood with

stage 4 (CD56^{bright}) and stage 5 (CD56^{dim}) NK cells. Due to the discovery of numerous tissue-resident NK cell subsets, it is becoming increasingly clear that NK cells are more heterogeneous than previously appreciated. These tissue-resident NK cell subsets each possess a unique phenotype and/or function, that are shaped by

local factors to enable homing and to suit the specific needs of the host organ. In order to ensure functionality and to prevent pathology, NK cell development is tightly regulated by an intricate network of transcription factors, which remains largely unknown in human. Here, we show that of the two principal isoforms of the transcriptional regulator RUNX2, the Type-I isoform is predominantly expressed during NK cell development. By knockdown and overexpression of RUNX2 in human HSC-based NK cell differentiation cultures, and by combining transcriptomics and flow cytometric analysis, we revealed

a crucial role of RUNX2 in human NK cell differentiation. RUNX2 stimulates and accelerates the generation of NK cells, possibly via the regulation of IL-2R β expression in committed progenitors. Furthermore, RUNX2 promotes a tissue-resident phenotype in differentiating NK cells and inhibits IFN- γ and TNF- α production. The direct involvement of RUNX2 in these processes is suggested by the RUNX2 ChIP-seq analysis of human NK cells.

15 INVITED TALK

Innate lymphoid cell (ILC)-differentiation and effector functions relative to T cells in inflammatory bowel disease

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The impact of intestinal inflammation on innate lymphoid cell (ILC)-differentiation and effector functions relative to T cells in humans remains largely unknown. We recently used single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNAseq) to identify a transcriptionally distinct population of naïve-like ILCs in the human colon (Mazzurana et al., Cell Res, 2021). Understanding of naïve ILC heterogeneity and the transcriptional, epigenetic and functional mechanisms that underlie ILC differentiation in tissues is crucial for understanding of ILC biology in health and disease. Here we present data demonstrating that CD62L distinguishes two subsets of quiescent and naïve-like CD45RA+ ILCs in tonsil tissue. While both subsets contain uni- and multipotent precursors of ILC1 and ILC3, CD62L+ ILCs are bona fide naïve ILCs with metabolism reminiscent of naïve T cells, lacking transcriptional and epigenetic signatures of mature ILCs. CD62L- ILCs are epigenetically similar to, but transcriptionally distinct from CD62L+ ILCs including transcripts of JAK/STAT signaling and metabolic pathways akin to mature ILCs. CD62L- quiescent and naïve-like ILCs with preferential differentiation capacity towards IL-22 producing ILC3 are accumulated in inflamed colon of adults with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). These data support a model where blood CD62L+ naïve ILCs that enter tissues lose CD62L and undergo tissue- and inflammation-induced imprinting that poises their differentiation potential. Our findings

identify restoration of homeostatic IL-22-producing ILC3 from CD62L- naïve-like ILCs as an approach to improve tissue healing in IBD.

Notably, we also observe an accumulation of CD62L- naïve-like ILCs in treatment-naïve pediatric (p)IBD patients, that correlates to inflammatory activity. scRNAseq unveiled further heterogeneity and inflammation-specific imprinting of colon ILCs as well as of NK cells and T cells. Specifically, ILCs show pronounced and unique transcriptional changes in inflammation, particularly those related to antigen-presentation. Furthermore, we identify a transcriptionally distinct innate-like T cell subset transcribing KLRF1 and additional NK-associated transcripts that is enriched in inflamed pIBD mucosa. A corresponding NK-like NKp80+ $\gamma\delta$ T cell population, expressing high levels of NK cell receptors and cytotoxic molecules, are also accumulated in adult IBD.

In conclusion, using a combination of high-dimensional single-cell analysis on the transcriptional and protein level, we provide a comprehensive characterization of ILCs and T cells in pediatric and adult IBD. Our findings contribute to increased understanding of intestinal inflammation and identify promising targets for IBD immunotherapy.

16 INVITED TALK**Tissue compartmentalization of NK cells and anti-viral immunity**

Donna Farber

Microbiology and Immunology, Columbia University, New York, USA. df2396@cumc.columbia.edu**17 SELECTED SHORT TALK****The unique properties of endometrial NK cells in preparation for pregnancy**Ee Von Woon¹, Victoria Male¹¹Imperial College London. e.woon19@imperial.ac.uk

Uterine Natural Killer cells (uNK) are the most abundant lymphocytes in the maternal-fetal interface during early pregnancy and are thought to play an important role in placental development. They interact with MHC Class I molecules on extravillous trophoblast cells via activating or inhibitory cell surface receptors (e.g. KIR, LILRB and CD94). As a result of this interaction, uNK is able to secrete cytokines (e.g. TNF- α , IL-8 and IFN- γ) that in turn regulate trophoblast invasion and spiral artery remodelling. More recently, interrogation of the placental bed by single cell RNA sequencing revealed three subpopulations of decidual Natural killer cells (dNK) which is postulated to have different roles in pregnancy. However, not much is known about the behaviour of uNK in the non-pregnant human endometrium which undergoes constant regeneration under hormonal influence in the menstrual cycle. Here, we used flow cytometry to study the phenotype and function of three subpopulations of uNK isolated from non-pregnant endometrium and decidua of first trimester pregnancy. To assess the ability of uNK to degranulate and produce cytokines, we stimulated the isolated leucocytes with PMA and ionomycin. We found no changes in proportions of uNK1-3 through the menstrual cycle, but there was relative increase of dNK1 in first trimester. During the menstrual cycle, expression of KIR and LILRB receptors on uNK1 were highest in secretory and menstrual phase compared to the proliferative phase and this was further increased in first trimester pregnancy. In contrast, expression of these receptors on uNK2 and 3 remained relatively steady through the menstrual cycle and increased proportionately in first trimester. Interestingly, uNK1 exhibited highest degranulation activity without stimulation during the menstrual phase, as measured by expression CD107a. Upon stimulation, all three subsets of uNK 1-3 demonstrated highest potential to degranulate and secrete TNF- α and IFN- γ during the

secretory phase. The changes in phenotype and function of uterine NK cells were not reflected in the CD56^{bright} and CD56^{dim} NK cells in the peripheral blood. Together, we have demonstrated that a subset of uNK can alter its phenotype and secretory function during the implantation phase of the menstrual cycle in preparation for interaction with trophoblasts in the event of successful embryo implantation. The role of uNK2 and uNK3 remain to be elucidated. Future research on clinical reproductive failure e.g. recurrent miscarriage or implantation failure should focus on this subset of uNK which may detect differences that were not evident in previous studies.

18 INVITED TALK

The role of NKG2D in development of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis and liver fibrosis

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Metabolic (dysfunction) associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD) is the most common chronic liver disease worldwide. It is a hepatic manifestation of metabolic syndrome, which includes insulin resistance, hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, hypertension and abdominal obesity. MAFLD is a spectrum of progressive liver disease from relatively benign steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), fibrosis, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). The key event in progression of MAFLD is activation of the immune system and development of inflammation. However, mediators and immune cells involved in early immune sensing of metabolically stressed liver cells are largely unknown.

To investigate the mechanism laying behind the transition from steatosis to NASH we developed a steatosis-steatohepatitis dietary (SSD) mouse model that mimics a western lifestyle. After 16 weeks of SSD feeding, we noticed several clinical hallmarks of liver damage such as hepatomegaly and elevated ALT levels when compared to chow-fed mice. Moreover, histological quantification revealed formation of micro- and macro-vesicular steatosis at early time points upon SSD onset and development of inflammatory foci, hepatocyte degeneration and hepatic

stellate cells (HSC) activation at later stages. This model closely resembles MAFLD progression in humans. *Ex vivo* stimulation of liver leukocytes revealed IL-17A as the most prominent cytokine that is increased early upon start of SSD. We identified hepatic $\gamma\delta$ T cells as a dominant source of IL-17A. TCR δ -/- mice showed reduced NASH and confirmed the importance of $\gamma\delta$ T cells in the disease progression. Furthermore, we found that metabolically stressed hepatocytes express high levels of NKG2D ligands on their surface, which suggested importance of NKG2D signaling axis in sensing of cellular stress. Indeed, employment of NKG2D-deficient mice showed striking reduction of liver inflammation and fibrosis. Altogether, activation of $\gamma\delta$ T cells via NKG2D plays a crucial first step in the progression of the disease and provide a potential new target for MAFLD treatment.

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19 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Effect of glucose-transporter inhibitors on the function of Natural Killer cells

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Glucose-transporter (Glut) inhibitors effectively inhibit the proliferation of different tumour cells and, as a result, prove to be anti-cancer therapeutics. Therefore, it is important to know, if these inhibitors also affect the anti-tumour function of natural killer (NK) cells. We treated NK cells with the Glut-1/2/3 specific inhibitor Glutor or with Glupin, which inhibits Glut-1 and -3 and analysed the energetic phenotype of these NK cells by Seahorse experiments. Glutor treatment resulted in higher

mitochondrial respiration, which could not be detected for Glupin. To examine the effect of Glut-inhibitors on NK cell effector functions, resting or pre-activated human NK cells were stimulated through the activating receptor CD16 in the presence or absence of Glutor or Glupin. Acute inhibition of the glucose-transporters had no significant effect on NK cell cytokine secretion or killing-capacity against different tumour cells. To analyse possible long-term effects, we cultured freshly isolated NK cells for 3

weeks in the presence or absence of Glutor or Glupin. We found a decreased proliferation of Glutor-treated NK cells. Furthermore, long-term treatment with Glutor impaired NK cell cytotoxicity and cytokine secretion, whereas Glupin-treated NK cells showed no difference in comparison to the control treated cells. The analysis of cytokine- and chemokine profile showed an increased

spontaneous secretion of MCP-1 and IL-8 after long-term treatment with Glutor. These data show that Glupin is a suitable candidate for cancer therapy, whereas Glutor seems ineligible due to its effect on NK cells.

20 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Metabolic requirements of NK cells during the response against retroviral infection

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Natural killer (NK) cells are innate immune cells and important early responders against viral infections and cancers. Changes in metabolism are crucial to fuel NK cell responses and altered metabolism is linked to NK cell dysfunction in obesity and cancer. It has been reported previously that a large neutral amino acid transporter, Slc7a5, is essential for the metabolic reprogramming of T cells and cytokine-activated NK cells. In addition to Slc7a5, the mineral iron has been described to be very important for immune functions and host defense as well as for essential cellular activities such as mitochondrial function including oxidative phosphorylation and enzymatic reactions that need iron as a cofactor. However, nothing is known about the metabolic requirements of NK cells during acute retroviral infection and their importance for antiviral immunity. Using the Friend retrovirus mouse model we show that following infection NK cells increase their nutrient uptake, including amino acids and iron,

and reprogram their metabolic machinery by increasing glycolysis and mitochondrial metabolism. We found that specific deletion of the amino acid transporter Slc7a5 in NK cells had discrete effects on NK cells, including reduced cytotoxicity. Furthermore, serum iron deficiency decreased the NK cell metabolic reprogramming and profoundly impaired antiviral functions leading to increased viral loads.

This study shows the requirement of nutrients and metabolism for the antiviral activity of NK cells and has important implications for viral infections associated with altered iron levels such as HIV and SARS-CoV-2. Our results will be relevant for drug developments targeting the NK cell metabolism to enhance their cytotoxic capacity against viruses and cancer cells.

21 INVITED TALK

Natural Killer Cells and Human Reproduction

Ashley Moffett

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The apposition of cells from two genetically different individuals occurs naturally during pregnancy. The mother and father generally differ in their HLA class I and class II types meaning that there is the potential for maternal allo-recognition of the fetus. T cells and Natural

Killer (NK) cells can both mediate allo-recognition using quite different mechanisms. The fetal cells providing a barrier throughout pregnancy that are in contact with maternal T and NK cells are trophoblast cells.

There are multiple ways that trophoblast cells avoid damaging maternal T cell responses and it seems highly unlikely that they all fail together to cause pregnancy failure in humans.

Dominating the maternal immune cells around the extravillous trophoblast (EVT) that invade into the decidua are specialised uterine NK cells. scRNA sequencing and CyTOF has revealed there are 3 main subsets. One subset has receptors (KIR) that can bind

to HLA-C molecules, the only polymorphic HLA molecule displayed by fetal EVT. The KIR gene family is also highly genetically variable with two main haplotypes (KIR A & B) present only in humans. The cooperation between uterine NK cells and EVT results in an allocation of resources between mother and fetus. This keeps the birth weight in a range that results in normal delivery of a fetus large enough to survive ex utero.

22 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Untimely TGF β -responses in severe COVID-19 inhibit NK cell function and NK cell-mediated control of SARS-CoV-2 replication

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SARS-CoV-2 is a single stranded RNA virus from the genus Betacoronavirus that causes Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). If symptomatic, the majority of infections are presenting as a mild to moderate flu-like illness of the upper and lower respiratory tract. About 14% of patients develop a more severe disease and 5% suffer critical symptoms including respiratory failure, multiorgan dysfunction and long term sequelae such as lung fibrosis. Given its largely acute course, components of the innate immune system are likely central in containing virus replication and in determining the course of the infection. Among components of the innate immune system, natural killer (NK) cells are an innate lymphocyte subset with notable activity against a broad range of viral infections. Available data show that NK cell function may be altered during COVID-19 despite an increase in activated and “adaptive” NK cells. It remains unknown why NK cell function is impaired in severe COVID-19 patients and if NK cells can contribute to SARS-CoV-2 virus control. Here, we show that NK cells can curtail SARS-CoV-2 replication but NK cells from severe COVID-19 patients failed to do so, because of a remarkable defect in cell-mediated cytotoxicity despite high level expression of cytotoxic effector molecules. Single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) profiles of NK cells along a time course of the entire COVID-19 disease spectrum revealed accelerated differentiation trajectories of NK cells towards terminally differentiated, functionally exhausted NK cells. Prominent among the enriched response pathways in NK cells from severe COVID-19 patients was a TGF β -response signature with reduced

expression of genes related to metabolic function, granule exocytosis and NK cell adhesion. TGF β -stimulated NK cells were unable to restrict SARS-CoV-2 virus replication and serum from severe COVID-19 patients inhibited NK cell function. Across the disease spectrum and time, serum TGF β peaked already during the first weeks in severe COVID-19 whereas mild cases showed lower TGF β -levels and a later peak. Neutralization of TGF β in patient serum restored NK cell function required for virus control. Our data reveal that untimely production of TGF β inhibits NK cell function and early virus control. Early inhibition of TGF β may be a strategy to restore virus control in severe cases of COVID-19.

23 SELECTED SHORT TALK

Persistent natural killer cell dysfunction in severe COVID-19

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Introduction: Longitudinal analyses of the innate immune system including earliest time points are essential to understand the immunopathogenesis and clinical course of COVID-19. The role of natural killer (NK) cells is not yet fully elucidated.

Material/Methods: To assess the impact of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the function and composition of the NK cell pool between moderate and severe COVID-19 over time (day 2-29 after symptom onset), we analyzed longitudinally collected peripheral blood samples from 72 patients and 50 controls (including 8 donors with flu-like symptoms) in three independent cohorts. Samples collected in cohort 1 were analyzed on the cellular level by multi-color flow cytometry (FC) and a microwell-based scRNA-seq approach (BD Rhapsody), while plasma levels of soluble factors were studied using a bead-based ultrasensitive immunoassay (Quanterix Simoa). Functional assays were performed with PMA/Ionomycin, IL-12/IL-15/IL-18, and K562 (FC detection of IFN- γ , TNF and CD107a) or coculture with human lung fibroblasts (FC detection of active Caspase-3) or SARS-CoV-2-infected VERO/Caco-2 cells (FC detection of spike-protein or SARS-CoV-2-specific genes via qPCR). In cohort 2 and 3, scRNA-seq was performed using a droplet-based platform (10x Chromium). Cohort 2 samples were additionally analyzed by mass cytometry (CyTOF) panel. Patients with dexamethasone or tocilizumab therapy were excluded from the analyses to avoid immunotherapy-induced biases in the results.

Results: We demonstrate NK cells in early severe COVID-19 to display signs of a strong IFN- α response

with increased expression of interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs) and genes related to IFN- α signaling, whereas in early moderate disease, NK cells were characterized by a TNF imprint. This differential gene expression pattern was specific for the first week after onset of symptoms and also enabled discrimination between patients with fatal outcomes of COVID-19 and those who finally recovered. Moreover, we demonstrate an impaired anti-SARS-CoV-2 NK cell activity which was particularly prominent and prolonged in severe COVID-19 and provide evidence for soluble factors involved in this NK cell dysfunction. Further, NK cell dysfunction may be relevant for development of fibrotic lung disease in severe COVID-19, as NK cells here exhibited impaired anti-fibrotic activity.

Conclusion: Collectively, our study points to differential IFN- α versus TNF responses as an important mechanism in the early phase of COVID-19 and describes a link between an exaggerated prolonged INF- α -induced NK cell response and persistent NK cell dysfunction with an unfavorable course of the disease.

24 SELECTED SHORT TALK

SARS-CoV-2-derived peptides regulate NK cell responses through HLA-E

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The ongoing severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic has led to more than 134 million confirmed cases and 2.9 million deaths to date (WHO, 2021-04-10). While the majority of infections lead to only mild symptoms, some patients develop severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which is characterized by systemic hyperinflammation. Since pathological aspects of severe COVID-19 are related to an excessive and mistargeted immune response, the initial interaction between the host's immune system and the virus-infected cells during the early stage of infection likely determines disease progression and severity.

As part of the "Karolinska KI/K Immune Atlas" project (covid19cellatlas.com/), we have previously demonstrated that natural killer (NK) cells are potently activated in COVID-19 patients (Maucourant et al., *Sci Immunol* 2020). However, the molecular mechanisms underlying NK cell activation during infection remain poorly understood and how NK cells detect SARS-CoV-2-infected cells at a molecular level is still unclear.

Here, we show that the genome of SARS-CoV-2 encodes for peptides that bind to HLA-E with remarkable efficiency. Functional interrogation of isolated NK cells

challenged with peptide-pulsed target cells revealed that SARS-CoV-2-derived peptides alter the NK cell response pattern via the NKG2 receptor family.

Given the prominent role of hyperinflammation in COVID-19, cytokine signals are likely key contributors to NK cell activity directed against SARS-CoV-2. Priming of NK cells from healthy donors with cytokines elevated in COVID-19 patients further shaped their response to SARS-CoV-2-derived peptides, resulting in specific contributions of distinct subsets.

Importantly, common cold-causing Coronaviruses including HKU1, OC43, NL63, and 229E display divergent peptide sequences and these peptides showed reduced binding capacity to HLA-E, suggesting a unique contribution of SARS-CoV-2 to the HLA-E peptide repertoire.

Collectively, our data indicate that SARS-CoV-2-derived peptides in concert with COVID-19-associated cytokines shape the NK cell response, potentially impacting on virus control and disease severity.

25 INVITED TALK

Harnessing innate immunity in cancer therapies: the example of Natural Killer Cell Engagers

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Most immunomodulatory approaches have focused on enhancing T-cell responses, by immune checkpoint inhibitors, chimeric antigen receptor T cells or bispecific antibodies. Although these therapies have led to

exceptional successes, only a minority of cancer patients benefit from these treatments, highlighting the need to identify new cells and molecules that could be exploited in the next generation of immunotherapy. Given the crucial role of innate immune responses in immunity, harnessing these responses opens up new possibilities for tumor control.

Antibody engineering provides us with great opportunities to induce synthetic immunity by harnessing the biological

functions of innate immune cells, in particular by boosting the capacity of Natural Killer (NK) cells to kill tumor cells directly and to stimulate T-cell responses indirectly. We designed NK cell engagers (NKCEs) to optimize NK cell antitumor functions by binding to NKp46 and CD16 activating receptors on NK cells, and one antigen on tumor cells (Gauthier et al., Cell 2019). We will present our progress on this NKCE platform.

26 SELECTED SHORT TALK

A dysfunctional program imprinted by PGE2 signaling shuts off NK cell communication pathways and disables immunosurveillance of metastasis

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Natural killer (NK) cells are key effector cells in the control of metastasis. This role reflects the ability of NK cells to rapidly detect and eliminate metastasizing tumor cells through targeted cytotoxicity and to produce immunostimulatory cytokines and chemokines (e.g. IFN γ , TNF α , XCL1 and CCL5) that further regulate anti-metastatic immunity. Recent work has demonstrated a critical role for the bioactive lipid prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) in immune evasion of primary tumors via suppression of intratumoral immunity and identified NK cells as a key cellular target of PGE2 signaling (Böttcher et al., Cell, 2018, Bonavita et al., Immunity 2020). However, how PGE2 signaling regulates NK cell biology and function and its consequences for NK cell-mediated control of metastasis have hardly been investigated so far. By using

transcriptional and epigenetic analyses, we show that PGE2 signaling on NK cells stably imprints a dysfunctional program characterized by the inability of NK cells to use key intercellular communication pathways upon their activation. Mechanistically, this program is governed by a transcription factor network downstream of PGE2 receptor signaling that seems to be conserved between mouse and human NK cells. We further reveal that *in vivo*, programming of NK cell dysfunctionality by PGE2-producing cancer cells located in early metastatic niches in the lung is critical for outgrowth of macrometastasis. Taken together, our data reveal a novel mechanism that could be exploited for anti-metastatic therapy.

27 INVITED TALK

Translating NK cell memory as cancer immunotherapy

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NK cell immunotherapy is a promising cellular therapy approach for cancer patients. Multiple laboratories have advanced our understanding of varying types of innate NK cell memory and memory-like responses over the

past decade, with a unifying definition of enhanced response to re-stimulation after an initial activation event. We identified that human cytokine-induced memory-like (memory) NK cells differentiate after a brief activation with

IL-12, IL-15, and IL-18 and have enhanced responses against leukemia and other cancer targets. Pre-clinical studies have demonstrated their enhanced anti-tumor potential *in vitro*, and *in vivo* in syngeneic murine models and human xenografts. We translated this concept into a first-in-human clinical trial that demonstrated safe adoptive transfer of donor memory NK cells for patients with relapsed or refractory acute myeloid leukemia (AML) resulting in complete remissions. Correlative mass cytometry revealed the memory NK cell multidimensional phenotype and identified NKG2A as a major checkpoint for memory NK cell response to AML. Additional clinical trials of donor memory NK cells the HCT setting have demonstrated safety and anti-leukemia activity the immune compatible setting and has

provided insights into persistence. CITE-seq single cell profiling reveals a unique memory NK cell transcriptomic signature. We have also developed approaches to gene edit and engineer memory-like NK cells with chimeric antigen receptors, expanding the spectrum of cancers for memory-like NK cellular therapy. Further, pairing with tumor targeting monoclonal antibodies can result in CAR-like responses via CD16/FcγRIIIa, providing additional activating signals that direct memory NK cell response. These studies identify a promising memory NK cell platform for cancer immunotherapy and highlight the importance of correlative studies during clinical trials to advance our understanding of human immunology.

Abstracts Short Talk Session

Short Talks I: ILCs and NK cells in Tissue

SHORT TALK 101

Tissue-Resident Clonal Expansions of Rhesus Macaque NK Cells

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Recent phenotypic, functional and transcriptomic analyses of natural killer (NK) cells in human and animals have established the presence of tissue resident NK(trNK) cells with specific characteristics and a central role in NK memory. The lack of endogenous clonal markers on NK cells impedes understanding the clonal genesis of trNKs. Transplantation of lentivirally-barcoded autologous hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells (HSPCs) has allowed tracking of NK cells at a clonal level in rhesus macaques (RM). We reported large KIR-restricted clonal expansions of mature CD56-CD16+NK in the peripheral blood (PB) of RM, clonally distinct from myeloid, T, B and CD56+16-NK, persisting for months to years, suggesting self-renewal independent of ongoing production from HSPCs (Wu et al, Cell Stem Cell, 2014 and Science Imm, 2018).

We now investigate the clonal distribution of NK cell populations in bone marrow (BM), liver, spleen, lymph nodes (LN), jejunum, colon and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL). We compared clonal patterns between various trNKs and PB NKs collected from barcoded RM. Tissue or PB NK were defined as CD3-CD14-CD20-NKG2+ (NKG2A+ and NKG2C+), and NK subsets were further sorted for CD16, CD56, CD49a, and CXCR3. The same expanded CD56-CD16+NK clones found in the PB were also detected at high abundance within BM, LN, liver and spleen CD56-CD16+NK. Strikingly, a group of markedly expanded trNK clones, distinct from the expanded CD56-CD16+NK clones present concurrently or previously in PB, were present and shared across all tissues examined. These clones were enriched in CD56-16+ trNK and absent in CD56+16- trNK. Notably, in both tissue and PB these clones were expanded in NKG2+ CD56-CD16- NK. These common expanded NK cells were specifically enriched in both tissue and PB CD56-16-CXCR3+NK, suggesting a role for this chemokine receptor. In contrast, CD49a expression did not enrich for these clones.

Clonally-expanded and persistent mature trNK cells, shared across multiple tissues but not present within PB mature CD56-CD16+NK subsets, combined with prior functional data suggesting NK memory is restricted to liver or other trNK cells suggests these clonally-expanded trNK cells may be of interest. The pattern of shared clones across tissues, together with identification of a rare PB NK subpopulation harboring the clones suggests preferential hematogenous homing of these clones to multiple tissues. Further analyses of gene expression and clonal dynamics are ongoing and should shed light on the ontology of trNK cells, with implications for the development of NK based immunotherapies and NK memory.

SHORT TALK 102**Modulation of tissue-niches of resident NK cells and ILC1s in response to infection**Tommaso Torcellan¹, Christin Friedrich¹, Rémi Doucet-Ladevèze¹, Sofie Riedmann¹, Georg Gasteiger¹¹Würzburg Institute of Systems Immunology (WüSI), Max Planck Research Group at the Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany. tommaso.torcellan@uni-wuerzburg.de

Most anatomical compartments of the body are subject to immune-surveillance by circulating and resident lymphocytes. Infection leads to a dramatic reorganization of the local network of immune cells including long-lasting effects best characterized for memory T cells which can persist at the site of previous infection and provide improved protection upon rechallenge. How infection affects the local pool of innate lymphocytes is less well understood. Natural Killer (NK) cells and ILC1s are an important early source of IFN γ during a wide range of bacterial and viral infections. We and others have recently shown that subsets of tissue-resident cells (trNKs) and ILC1s exist in multiple organs of mice and

humans. Here we used genetic tracing and confocal microscopy to characterize the tissue niches of trNK cells and ILC1s in different organs, including the salivary glands, female reproductive tract, small intestine and skin. We performed local infections and tracked the gene expression programs and localization of ILCs and NK cells in the tissue. Our data suggest that infection leads to a reorganization of the tissue-niches of NK cells and ILCs and thereby improves early immunity in barrier organs.

SHORT TALK 103**The role of IL-22 and IL-22 producing immune cells in the uterus**Antonia O. Cuff¹, Victoria Male¹¹Imperial College London; a.cuff@imperial.ac.uk

Background: IL-22 is important for maintaining the integrity of mucosal epithelium following bacterial challenge and is the major cytokine product of type 3 innate lymphoid cells (ILC) or ILC3. IL-22 represses early labour in mice and decreases in human blood as a woman progresses from the third trimester of a pregnancy into labour. This suggests IL-22, and by extension ILC3, may act to maintain pregnancy. Here we explore the dynamics of ILC3 in the lining of the uterus across the menstrual cycle and pregnancy.

Method: Uterine leukocytes were isolated at different timepoints across the menstrual cycle and pregnancy, and leukocyte phenotype and cytokine production analysed by flow cytometry. Further analyses of the potential effect of IL-22 on uterine mucosal epithelium were conducted by reanalysing publicly available scRNA seq data, and IL-22 receptor expression confirmed using flow cytometry.

Results: Uterine ILC3 frequency and cell number fluctuate over the menstrual cycle and pregnancy, with ILC3 peaking during the menstrual phases when the lining of the uterus undergoes repair; proliferative and secretory menstrual phases. Since ILC3 accumulate

during these phases, these are the timepoints where their function is most likely to be important. On cytokine assessment, ILC3 produce relatively similar amounts of IL-22 across the timepoints analysed, although innate T cells tend to produce more IL-22 than ILC3, which may therefore have a greater contribution towards the wider uterine IL-22 pool. Further analyses of IL-22 responsive cells revealed pregnancy-related epithelial subsets have differential expression of IL-22 receptor subunits across pregnancy, IL10R β and IL22R α 1, suggesting differential responsiveness to IL-22 from the beginning compared to the end of a pregnancy. Furthermore, uterine CD127- ILC3 have a similar phenotype and function to conventional uterine CD127+ ILC3 and may represent a transitory population related to conventional CD127+ ILC3. Uterine CD127+ and CD127- ILC3 differ in compartments of the lining of the uterus during the third trimester at term, implying differential roles may exist in these anatomical sites at term.

SHORT TALK 104**Increased frequency of IL-17A producing ILC3 in duodenal mucosa in familial adenomatous polyposis**

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Background: Familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP), a hereditary gastrointestinal tumor syndrome induced by a mutation in the APC gene, is characterized by the presence of myriads of adenomatous colorectal polyps that inevitably progress to colorectal cancer without (procto) colectomy. Apart from affecting the colon, FAP is also associated with a variety of extracolonic manifestations, including duodenal adenomas and adenocarcinomas. Of note, there is a lack of a clear genotype-phenotype association suggesting the existence of yet unidentified factors that contribute to the onset and progression of the disease.

Given their role in maintaining mucosal homeostasis and integrity and in light of the increasing data indicating a role in tumorigenesis, we studied the composition and function of the duodenal innate lymphocyte (ILC) compartment in FAP patients.

Patients/Methods: A total of 72 FAP patients were enrolled into this study. ILCs were isolated from macroscopically

normal and adenomatous tissue samples obtained during routine endoscopy and then assessed regarding phenotype and function by FACS. In addition, mucosal cytokine mRNA levels were studied by rt-PCR.

Results: We found FAP to be associated with a significantly increased frequency of ILCs even in macroscopically normal duodenal mucosa compared to controls. In particular, the number of group 3 ILCs was increased and associated with the extent of duodenal polyposis. In colon tissue from FAP patients, by contrast, we found frequency of ILC3 to be significantly decreased, indicating a compartment specific effect. Functional characterization revealed an increased production of IL-17A by duodenal but not colonic ILC3 in FAP.

Conclusion: Our data suggest IL-17A producing ILC3 to be involved in duodenal adenoma formation in FAP.

SHORT TALK 105**Memory like ILC1s during repeated liver damage**

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Innate lymphoid cells can also mediate memory-like responses. While the liver seems to be involved in memory responses of NK cells, much less is known about memory-like responses of ILC1 during repeated liver damage. To investigate this, we established a mouse model where we injected 1.6g/kg Carbon tetrachloride (CCI4) to induce liver damage. Acute liver damage upon one CCI4 injection was quickly repaired and did not result in changes of liver ILCs. In contrast, repeated liver damage by injecting CCI4 three times in intervals of one month to allow for recovery of the damage in between injections resulted in an increase of IL-7Ra+ CD200+

ILC1s as detected by flow cytometry. Liver ILC1s were not only increased in absolute numbers but they also showed enhanced IFN γ production in comparison to control groups (untreated, oil and acute CCI4 control). This increase of more functional liver ILC1s after repeated liver injury was very transient, as it was most prominent 24 hours after the last injection of CCI4. We did not observe increased staining for the proliferation marker Ki67 of IL-7Ra+ CD200+ ILC1s, suggesting that the increase is not mediated by proliferation of these cells. We hypothesize that ILC1s migrate to the liver after repeated CCI4 treatment possibly from the gut via

the liver-gut axis. Supporting this hypothesis, we found that the IL-7R α + CD200r+ ILC1s were also positive for IL-18Ra+ and cKit+. However, the exact origin and the functional role of these ILC1s needs to be clarified.

SHORT TALK 106

The Aryl-hydrocarbon Receptor-dependent Regulation of Innate Lymphoid Cell Responses in Skin Inflammation

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Contact hypersensitivity (CHS) is an animal model of allergic dermatitis, in which a small chemical molecule – hapten generates memory response upon penetration of the epidermal barrier of the skin. It was shown that memory reaction can be mediated by both adaptive Th1 and CD8+ T cells, as well as by innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) that reside in the liver. The aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) is a ligand-activated transcription factor widely expressed in various tissues including skin, where it responds to both exogenous and endogenous ligands. Both skin and liver ILCs express AhR, and can respond to its ligands. Here, we show that AhR expression in NKp46+ cells contributes to the resolution of skin

inflammation evoked by CHS memory reaction. Mice deficient in AhR in NKp46-expressing cells present a memory response comparable to control mice, but display a delayed resolution of inflammation. This phenotype depended on the presence of adaptive immune cells and correlated with higher tissue damage and expression of inflammatory cytokines and infiltration of inflammatory cells. These data indicate that AhR activation in Innate lymphocytes contributes to the resolution of T cell-mediated skin inflammation during CHS recall response, and could be explored for potential targeting of skin allergic diseases.

SHORT TALK 107

Innate Lymphocytes Regulate Immune Functions of Liver Sinusoidal Endothelial Cells

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Liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSECs) form the blood vessels connecting the portal vein, the hepatic artery and the hepatic vein in the liver. LSECs are distinguished from other ECs by the lack of a basement membrane, presence of fenestrae, and formation of discontinuous blood vessels. In sinusoids, LSECs are located in the close proximity to immune cells, including circulating natural killer (NK) cells and distinct subsets of tissue-resident innate lymphoid cells (ILCs). The role of LSECs

in immunology has been mainly studied in the context of T cell-mediated responses, showing that LSECs might be instrumental for maintaining liver immune tolerance through regulation of the T cell compartment. However, the interaction between LSECs and NK/ILCs is poorly understood. The goal of our study is to investigate the mechanisms involved in NK/ILC-LSEC crosstalk in homeostasis and in liver diseases.

Our results revealed that in steady-state LSECs expressed heterogeneous levels of major histocompatibility complex class II (MHC II), which is important for antigen presentation to CD4+ helper T cells. Lyve1+ midzonal LSECs expressed higher amounts of MHC II compared to periportal and pericentral cells. MHC II-high and MHC II-low/- LSECs also displayed distinct transcriptomic profiles, suggesting both spatial and functional segregation of endothelial cells in the liver. We observed that the maintenance of MHC II expression on LSECs both *in vitro* and *in vivo* depended on the presence

of the inflammatory cytokine IFN- γ and the master transcriptional co-activator CIITA, reported to regulate MHC II gene expression in an IFN- γ -dependent manner. LSECs from T and B cell-deficient mice presented unaltered expression of MHC II, while the mice that in addition lacked innate lymphocytes displayed reduced MHC II levels on LSECs, comparable to IFN- γ -deficient animals. These data identify NK cells and ILCs as the potential major source of IFN γ in steady-state in the liver, with role to maintain MHC II expression on LSECs.

Session II: NK Cell Functions I

SHORT TALK 108

Donor lymphocytes in peripheral blood of patients after lung transplantation comprise high frequencies of KIR-positive T and NK cell subsets

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For end-stage lung diseases, lung transplantation (LuTx) is the only curative treatment option. Acute and chronic rejections are major limitations. A deeper understanding of the contribution of immune responses early after LuTx is urgently needed. Passenger leukocytes, derived from donor lungs and migrating into the recipients' periphery, are primarily NK and T cells. Our aim was to characterize KIR expression, regulating NK and CD8+ T cell activity, on donor and recipient NK and T cells in recipient blood after LuTx. Moreover, we investigated the functional capacity of donor vs. recipient NK cells.

Peripheral blood samples at pre, T0hr, T24hrs and 3wks post Tx of 51 LuTx recipients were analyzed for the presence of HLA-mismatched donor cells and their KIR repertoire as well as activation status using flow cytometry. These results were correlated with clinical parameters, i.e. primary graft dysfunction (PGD) and cold ischemic times (CIT).

Within the first 3wks after LuTx, donor NK and T cells were detected in n=51 patients with a peak at T0hr. An increase of the KIR2DL1-positive subset was detected within the donor NK cell repertoire. Moreover, donor NK cells showed significantly higher frequencies of KIR2DL1-positive cells ($p < 0.01$) 3wks post LuTx compared to recipient NK cells. This effect was also observed in

donor T cells 3wks after LuTx with higher proportions of KIR2DL1- ($p < 0.05$) and KIR3DL1- ($p < 0.01$) positive T cells. Higher activation levels of donor NK and T cells ($p < 0.001$) were detected as compared to recipient cells via CD25 expression as well as enhanced degranulation capacity upon activation by K562 target cells. The KIR repertoire on donor NK and T cells in LuTx recipient blood does not correlate with PGD, while the frequencies of KIR+ donor NK cells increased directly after LuTx with longer CIT.

Higher frequencies of donor NK and T cells expressing KIR compared to recipient NK and T cells argue for their origin in the lung as part of a highly specialized immunocompetent compartment. Despite KIR expression, the activation level of donor NK and T cells in the periphery of the recipient may be higher compared to recipient cells. Moreover, a positive correlation was detected for KIR surface expression on NK cells and CIT but not PGD implying extended preservation times have an impact on the NK subset composition. Donor NK and T cells might have a regulatory effect in the balance between tolerance and rejection as well as graft survival after LuTx.

SHORT TALK 109**Influence of HCMV variants expressing NKG2D ligands on immune cell activation**

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Introduction: HCMV infection elicits protective NK and T cell responses. Patients with inherited or acquired NK/T cell impairments, e.g. recipients of organ transplants under immunosuppression, are at high risk of HCMV infection. A protective HCMV vaccine – that is currently not available – would not only greatly reduce the risk for HCMV reactivation and disease in those patients, but also lower the incidence of graft rejection. An effective HCMV vaccine should be able to induce HCMV-specific protective T cells, and this property might be combinable with strong attenuation, mediated by NK cell responses.

Objective: We aimed at comparing the NKG2D ligand ULBP2 expressed by HCMV mutants in the presence/absence of immune evasins for HLA molecules that are expected to differ in their ability to activate NK cells and HCMV-specific CD8⁺ T cells, respectively.

Material & Methods: ULBP2-expressing mutants based on the parental TB40 strain (Δ US2-6) were constructed by replacing the UL16 gene with the ULBP2 transgene driven by a weak or strong promoter. Fibroblasts infected with WT TB40 or the mutants were phenotypically characterized with respect to HLA class I and NK ligands (ULBP1, ULBP2, MICA/B, CD155), and secretion of soluble ULBP2 into culture supernatants was analyzed

by quantitative ELISA. Furthermore, we co-cultured fibroblasts infected with these ULBP2-expressing variants with allogeneic PBMCs to measure NK/T cell responses.

Results: Owing to the presence of US11, downregulation of HLA class I expression occurred in all infected cells. Fine-tuned, increased surface expression of ULBP2 was observed for the weak- and strong ULBP2-expressing mutants, but not the parental strain due to UL16-mediated retention. Significantly increased shedding of ULBP2 was detected for the ULBP2 mutants mirroring the expression level of the transgene. NK, CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells were activated by the HCMV variants as evidenced by upregulation of CD69 and CD25. Upon interaction with ULBP2, a significant down-modulation of NKG2D was observed on both NK and T cells and the intensity correlated with weak or strong ULBP2 expression.

Conclusion: Expression of NKG2D ligands to achieve attenuation while simultaneously induces HCMV-specific T cells by deleting HLA-I immune evasins represents a promising approach for HCMV vaccine development.

SHORT TALK 110**Liver organoids as a model system to study immune cell recognition of HBV-infected Hepatocytes**

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Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within the HLA-DP genomic region have been described as main genetic risk factor for the outcome of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection, with HLA-DPB1*04:01 being a protective and HLA-DPB1*03:01 a risk allele for establishing chronic HBV. We recently identified functional interactions between the natural killer cell (NK cell) receptor NKp44 and a subset of HLA-DP molecules, including HLA-DP401 but not HLA-DP301, implicating a role for NKp44/HLA-DP interactions in HBV disease outcomes.

The aim of this project was to establish a liver organoid model to study expression of HLA-DP during HBV infection and determine consequences of HLA-DP expression on infected hepatocytes for recognition by NKp44+ NK cells.

Liver organoids were generated by enzymatic digestion of liver tissue derived from patients undergoing tumor resection and cultured as previously described. Liver organoids expressed hepatocyte markers including Na⁺-taurocholate cotransporting polypeptide (NTCP), on mRNA and protein level. NTCP expression is essential for HBV infection indicating permissibility of generated liver organoids to HBV infection. For HBV infection, liver organoids were exposed to plasma from HBVpos individuals, and secretion of HBV DNA and proteins were determined upon infection. Supernatant of infected organoids contained HBV DNA, HBeAg and HBsAg following infection, which was absent in supernatant of

mock controls, indicating productive HBV infection of liver organoids that was further confirmed by detection of intracellular HBV DNA within infected organoids. While liver sections from HBVpos individuals displayed high levels of HLA-DP in comparison to sections from HBVneg individuals, *in vitro* HBV infection of liver organoids did not induce HLA-DP expression on infected hepatocytes. IFN- γ has been described to induce HLA class II expression also in non-hematopoietic cells, therefore we assessed HLA-DP-expression on liver organoids after IFN- γ exposure. HLA-DP was upregulated on liver organoids after stimulation with IFN- γ , indicating that IFN- γ production is required to induce HLA-DP-expression following HBV infection. To determine the consequences of HLA-DP-upregulation on hepatocytes for recognition by primary NKp44+ NK cells, we quantified *in vitro* NK cell degranulation after co-incubation with HLA-DP molecules presenting HBV-derived peptides. NKp44+ NK cells demonstrated an upregulation of CD107a after co-incubation with HLA-DP-HBV peptide complexes, which was abrogated by pre-incubation with an anti-NKp44 blocking antibody.

In conclusion, human liver organoids can be productively infected with HBV, providing an *in vitro* model system to study the molecular mechanisms by which NK cells recognize HBV-infected hepatocytes and to determine the functional correlates of protective host genetic factors.

SHORT TALK 111

Natural Killer cell-mediated ADCC in SARS-CoV-2-infected individuals and vaccine recipients

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COVID-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has emerged as a global pandemic. While immune responses of the adaptive immune system have been in the focus of research, the role of NK cells in COVID-19 remains poorly understood. NK cells can respond to virus-infected cells with a variety of activating receptors and are capable of inducing cell death and releasing soluble factors such as

cytokines, perforin and granzyme. Here we determined whether NK cells can mediate SARS-CoV-2 antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC), using a CD107a degranulation assay to quantify CD16-mediated NK cell activation in response to antibodies directed against SARS-CoV-2 spike-1 (S1) and nucleocapsid (NC) protein. Serum samples from SARS-CoV-2-positive

individuals induced significant CD107a expression by NK cells in response to S1 and NC antibodies, while serum samples from SARS-CoV-2-negative individuals did not. Furthermore, serum samples from individuals that received the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine BNT162b2 also induced strong CD107a expression by NK cells that increased with the second vaccination and was higher than observed in infected individuals. As expected, vaccine-induced responses were only directed against S1 and not against NC protein. Interestingly, screening of

serum samples that were collected prior to the COVID-19 pandemic identified two individuals with cross-reactive antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 S1, which also induced degranulation of NK cells. Taken together, these data demonstrate that antibodies induced by COVID-19 and anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccines can trigger NK cell-mediated ADCC activity, and also identify some cross-reactive ADCC activity against SARS-CoV-2 by endemic coronavirus-specific antibodies.

SHORT TALK 112

Priming of NK cell effector function by macrophages in HIV-1 infection

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Introduction

Natural Killer (NK) cells are an integral part of the innate defense against viral infections. Despite their high cytotoxic potential, NK cells do not kill HIV-1 infected cells effectively. In certain infections, NK cells require the help of accessory cells to become activated and successfully eliminate infected cells. Previous studies showed that pathogen primed macrophages enhance both NK cell cytotoxicity and production of proinflammatory cytokines via co-stimulatory ligands such as CD48 or CD80. Here, we investigated how HIV-1 infection affects macrophage priming of NK cell effector function.

Methods: Monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) were differentiated from peripheral blood with M-CSF for 7 days. MDM were then infected with the HIV-1 strain 89.6 for 5 days or stimulated with the TLR7/8 ligand CL097. As a control, an inflammatory macrophage phenotype was induced by stimulation with LPS and IFN γ for 24 h. Next, HIV-1-infected and LPS/IFN γ -stimulated MDM were co-cultured with autologous resting NK cells for 24 h. After co-culture, NK cell cytotoxicity and cytokine production were measured against the HLA class I deficient 721.221 target cell line in a 6 h degranulation assay. Additionally, the modulation of MDM surface markers in response to HIV-1 infection, CL097 or LPS/IFN γ activation was assessed via multiparameter flow cytometry.

Results: The strongest upregulation of the co-stimulatory ligands CD48, CD80 and the stress-ligands ULBP2/5/6 and MIC-A/B was induced by LPS/IFN γ treatment of MDM. Low level HIV-1 infection with HIV-1 89.6 (up to 3.66% p24+ cells of total MDM culture) also resulted in an upregulation of CD48 and CD80 – albeit to lower levels compared to LPS/IFN γ – and in a moderate

increase of NKG2D-ligand expression compared to untreated macrophages. These effects were similar to TLR7/8 stimulation alone. After MDM-NK co-culture, MDM[LPS/IFN γ]-primed NK cells showed an increase in both degranulation (as measured by CD107a) and cytokine production (IFN γ , TNF α and CCL4) in response to 721.221. NK cells primed by MDM[HIV-1] showed increased CD107a expression and increased intracellular staining of CCL4 and TNF α compared to NK cells co-cultured with untreated MDM – with the priming effect being most pronounced for CCL4 production.

Conclusion: Pathogen-activated macrophages have the capability to directly influence NK cell function. Low-level HIV-1 infection of MDM enhanced the production of the CCR5 ligand CCL4 and TNF α by NK cells against HLA-class I deficient targets. Increased proinflammatory cytokine production after macrophage priming in the context of HIV-1 infection may enhance viral control but also drive infection-associated inflammation.

SHORT TALK 113

Expression of NKG2D by NK and NKT cells by cutaneous leishmaniasis patients before and after treatment

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Natural Killer (NK) cells are part of the innate immune response and are major producers of cytokines, acting on the recruitment and activation of other immune cells to fight infection. NKT cells are T lymphocytes that have characteristics of both these cells and NK cells, thus adding functions of these two cell types. These cells are responsible for making a connection between innate and adaptive responses and correspond to 0.1-0.5% of peripheral blood leukocytes. NKG2D is an activation marker, being a molecule that indicates that a cell has experienced a stress episode. The present study aimed to evaluate, by flow cytometry, the expression of NKG2D by NK and NKT cells in cutaneous leishmaniasis patients before (BT) and after treatment (PT) with Glucantime. For this, blood was drawn in heparin tubes and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) were separated using the Ficoll gradient. After staining with surface antibodies (CD3, CD16, CD56 and NKG2D), the samples were acquired in a FACSARIA III (100.000 events/tube) using the software "Facs Diva 8.0" (BD Bioscience) for data acquisition and the software FlowJo 7.6.5 (@Tree Star Inc.) for data analysis. A decrease in the expression of NKG2D markers by NK CD16- cells was observed in the

BT group, when compared with the CT group ($p=0.0003$). Regarding the expression of the NKG2G marker in NK cells (CD16+CD56+), there was less expression in the cells of BT patients, when compared to the PT ($p=0.0420$) and CT ($p=0.0101$) groups. When evaluating the expression of the NKG2D marker in NKT CD8+ and NKT CD4+ cells, a lower expression in the BT group was observed when compared with the CT group ($p=0.0101$ and $p=0.0020$, respectively). When evaluating the expression of this marker in NKT DN cells, we also observed a low expression in BT patients, when compared with the CT group ($p=0.0231$). In summary, our data suggest that NK and NKT cells appear to be influenced by Leishmania infection, decreasing their activation potential. This fact may be bad for the patient since these cells are major producers of cytokines, that help to dictate the developed immune response, what may lead to an impaired cellular immune response. The way that Leishmania interferes with the activation of NK and NKT cells needs to be better investigated, to understand the role of these cells in the fight or progression of the infection.

SHORT TALK 114

Engagement of CD56 can stimulate Natural Killer cell responses

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CD56 is expressed on the majority of human NK cells and is widely used as NK cell marker. The functional role of CD56 on NK cells, however, is not yet fully explored. In a previous study, the stimulation with anti-CD56 antibodies led to the activation of pre-activated, but not resting NK cells. Using CD56 knock-out NK cells we show that this activation through an anti-CD56 antibody was specific. Based on alternative splicing, different isoforms of CD56 such as NCAM120, NCAM140 or NCAM180 can be generated. We did not find any differences

in the expression of CD56 isoforms between resting and pre-activated NK cells. However, our data show differences in CD56 glycosylation, which might explain the different responsiveness of resting versus activated NK cells. Furthermore, stimulation of resting NK cells with cytokines such as IL-2 + IL-15 or IL-12 + IL-15 + IL-18 can induce their reactivity for CD56 stimulation. To analyse the downstream signalling of CD56, we treated pre-activated NK cells with several inhibitors against different signalling molecules. Inhibition of Syk, PI3K,

Erk and src-family-kinases impaired CD56-mediated NK cell stimulation. To analyse the influence of CD56 on the killing-capacity of NK cells, we performed killing-assays of CD56 knockout or wt NK cells against different tumour

cells. The killing-capacity of NK cells was not affected by the absence of CD56, demonstrating that the stimulating effect of CD56 on activated NK cells does not have a major impact on their cytotoxic activity.

Session III: NK Cells and Cancer I

SHORT TALK 115

Enhancing functionality of NK cells towards colorectal cancer cell lines

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The World Health Organisation reported 935,000 deaths over the year 2020 caused by colorectal and rectal cancer. There is a high need to develop novel curative treatments for patients especially with metastatic disease non-responsive to current treatments. Allogeneic natural killer (NK) cells have shown to be safe and effective in targeting tumors and they do not cause graft versus host disease. However, the treatment of solid tumors is challenging due to their immunosuppressive microenvironment. Introduction of chimeric antigen receptors (CAR) to NK cells, stands out as one of the most promising approaches to overcome this resistance. In this study, we investigated the potency of our umbilical cord blood derived NK cell (UCB-NK) product (GTA002) against various colorectal cancer cell lines. Tumor antigen positive cell lines were subsequently targeted by CAR NK cells (GTA102) to investigate the efficiency of antigen-specific targeting of resistant tumor cells.

Potency of GTA-002 against the colorectal cancer cell lines SW480, HT29, HCT116, LOVO, LS174T, SW48 and COLO205 was tested in a luminescence cell viability assay; in the IncuCyte live cell imaging platform (2D, n=7 and 3D, n=6) and in the Cytoflex LX flowcytometer. CARs were developed and delivered in UCB derived CD34+ cells by a 3rd generation lentiviral system. CAR mediated anti-tumor responses and cellular avidity was measured by flowcytometry and the Z-movi, respectively.

Luminescence data showed refractoriness of the tumor cell lines HT29 and HCT116 to GTA-002, which was confirmed by the kinetic analysis (2D) and flowcytometry data. Potency of GTA-002 was observed against tightly formed spheroid CRC cultures in a kinetic image-based

analysis. Additionally, we developed an NK cell line (KHYG1) based reporter system and demonstrated significant CAR mediated enhanced targeting of the antigen+ resistant tumor cell lines when compared to unmodified cells. Initial transduction experiments in CD34+ cells, showed stable expression of eGFP and CAR during the first weeks of expansion and differentiation into CD56+ NK-cells and no impairment of innate NK cell potency.

In conclusion, CRC cell lines exhibited differential sensitivity/responsiveness profile in the 2D and 3D settings. It is essential to evaluate the potency of cell-based immunotherapy products in both 2D and 3D settings to target solid tumors efficiently. Most importantly, our results demonstrate that introduction of CAR to NK cells significantly improves targeting of UCB-NK cell resistant antigen+ CRC cells and stands out as a potential cell therapy product for the treatment of colorectal cancer patients.

SHORT TALK 116

Oxygen concentration significantly alters NK cell phenotype and function: implications for immunotherapy within the solid tumor microenvironment

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Natural Killer (NK) cell-based treatments have had therapeutic success for hematological malignancies but strategies to treat solid tumors have been more limited due to immune suppression within the tumor microenvironment (TME). An important and understudied aspect of this suppression is the low oxygen environment created by proliferating tumor cells. To study the effect of oxygen concentration on NK cell function, we used the novel AVATARTM system to model oxygen levels of three key tissues that NK cells inhabit *in vivo*: the peripheral blood (12% O₂), the bone marrow (5% O₂) and the TME (1% O₂). All comparisons were made against a standard incubator condition. NK cells were cultured in low dose IL-15 (1ng/ml) and incubated for three different time points: 24 hours, 72 hours and 7 days. NK cells incubated at 1% O₂ have decreased proliferation and cytotoxicity compared to NK cells incubated at higher oxygen conditions. We observed decreases in natural cytotoxicity against K562 targets and antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity (ADCC) against Raji targets with rituximab. To assess what contributes to these changes, we conducted a mass cytometry (CyTOF) analysis, real time imaging assays, metabolic assays and gene expression (RNA-seq and ATAC-seq) analysis. The CyTOF analysis revealed oxygen dependent changes

in expression of activating receptors, Ki-67, perforin and granzyme. CD122 expression was decreased under hypoxia making NK cells less responsive to IL-15 signaling. The addition of high dose IL-15 (10ng/ml) or IL-15 activation in the context of an NK cell engager or induced pluripotent stem cell derived NK cell (iNK) was able to rescue defects in killing. Under hypoxic conditions, NK cell metabolism resembled cancer cell metabolism with increased glycolysis as measured using a Seahorse assay. These changes are accompanied by decreased mitochondrial mass and increased reactive oxygen species. Gene expression analysis revealed that changes in NK cell metabolism and function are mediated at the epigenetic level by histone demethylases. Treatment with histone demethylase inhibitors rescued NK cell cytotoxicity as measured using an InCuCyte machine. These results indicate that NK cells who enter the TME are fundamentally different than those in the bone marrow or blood stream. The insights gained from this study will be leveraged to overcome hypoxia induced immune suppression in the TME to enhance NK cell-based immunotherapy for solid tumors.

SHORT TALK 117

Identification of specific gene expression regulation during activation and cancer cell killing of oNKord® Natural Killer cells by transcriptome analysis and comparison with cytotoxic potential.

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Glycostem Therapeutics (Oss, the Netherlands) has developed a novel, off-the shelf, allogeneic Natural Killer (NK)-cell based cancer immunotherapy (oNKord®) for the treatment of hematological malignancies and solid tumors. oNKord® is produced in a multi-step process, starting from fresh umbilical cord blood-derived CD34+ hematopoietic stem cells, isolated and expanded *ex vivo* and then differentiated into functional NK cells in a feeder cell-free culture system. oNKord® safety

and efficacy against acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is currently being evaluated in the WiNK Phase I/II clinical trial (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT04632316).

oNKord® batches are each generated from a single CD34+ hematopoietic stem cells donor and show similar patterns of expression for cell surface receptors and potent *in vitro* cytotoxicity against various tumor cell lines. Nevertheless, the interindividual variability between

CD34+ cells donors can result in heterogeneous batches with dissimilar growth and functionality, that cannot be predicted beforehand. Therefore, we investigated the biological variability between oNKord® batches by comparing *in vitro* cytotoxicity against cancer cell lines with transcriptome profiling of several oNKord® products. Hence, we generated 10 oNKord® batches, for which we monitored relevant parameters as cell expansion, differentiation progression, cell purity, impurity, and receptor phenotype. Next, we challenged each batch with multiple cancer cell lines (from both solid and hematological tumors) and analyzed their cytotoxic potential. In parallel, we performed total RNA isolation from challenged and unchallenged oNKord® cells and we performed transcriptome analysis with RNA-sequencing, using an Illumina HiSeq 4000 platform.

Using differential expression analysis, we compared the profiles of challenged vs unchallenged cells and we identified specific gene expression signatures for challenged oNKord®. Additionally, the comparison of

the transcriptome profile with the cytotoxicity potential of the 10 oNKord® products allowed us to identify gene expression differences which define 'excellent' and 'neutral' killers.

It is crucial for NK cell immunotherapy to get an understanding of the molecular pathways which turn on/off after cell activation and during the killing process, and their correlation with the product phenotype and cytotoxic potential. This can significantly improve our knowledge about oNKord® and its batch-related functionality. From such data sets, we will provide statistic rationales to prove the criteria to be used to identify the 'excellent' products and to support strategies to be used to improve the homogeneity and the performances of all oNKord® batches.

SHORT TALK 118

The macrophage tetraspan MS4A4A enhances Dectin-1-dependent NK cell-mediated resistance to metastasis

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The plasma membrane tetraspan molecule MS4A4A is selectively expressed by macrophage-lineage cells, but its function is unknown. Here we report that MS4A4A was restricted to murine and human mononuclear phagocytes and was induced during monocyte-to-macrophage differentiation in the presence of interleukin 4 or dexamethasone. Human MS4A4A was co-expressed with M2/M2-like molecules in subsets of normal tissue-resident macrophages, infiltrating macrophages from inflamed synovium and tumor-associated macrophages. MS4A4A interacted and colocalized with the β -glucan receptor dectin-1 in lipid rafts. In response to dectin-1

ligands, Ms4a4a-deficient macrophages showed defective signaling and defective production of effector molecules. In experimental models of tumor progression and metastasis, Ms4a4a deficiency in macrophages had no impact on primary tumor growth, but was essential for dectin-1-mediated activation of macrophages and natural killer (NK) cell-mediated metastasis control. Thus, MS4A4A is a tetraspan molecule selectively expressed in macrophages during differentiation and polarization, essential for dectin-1-dependent activation of NK cell-mediated resistance to metastasis.

SHORT TALK 119**The role of cDC1/NK cell communication within the tumor microenvironment for anti-cancer Immunity**

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Conventional type 1 dendritic cells (cDC1) play a crucial role in anti-tumor immunity. cDC1 abundance within tumor tissue positively correlates with cancer patient survival and is predictive of the responsiveness to cancer immunotherapy. Recently, we investigated the mechanisms responsible for cDC1 accumulation in immunogenic tumors, which are susceptible to cDC1-mediated immune control. In these tumors, cDC1 are recruited into the tumor microenvironment by the chemokines CCL5 and XCL1, produced by natural killer (NK) cells within the tumor tissue. This NK cell/chemokine/cDC1 axis was associated with tumor rejection in mice and survival of human cancer patients, suggesting an

important function of cDC1 that is carried out locally within the tumor tissue. However, the spatio-temporal dynamics of cDC1 within the tumor tissue and their local interaction with other immune cells are not yet fully understood. Interestingly, chemokine production by NK cells did not only regulate cDC1 accumulation but strongly impacted on cDC1 positioning within the tumor microenvironment, resulting in NK/cDC1 cluster formation. These clusters also harbor cytotoxic T cells, which play a critical role for tumor rejection. Here, we investigate the mechanisms that regulate formation of these multicellular clusters, and the relevance of local immune cell cross-talk within these clusters for anti-cancer immunity.

SHORT TALK 120**Exploring the role of fractalkine (CX3CL1) in natural killer cell cell chemotaxis and phenotype in obesity associated cancers.**

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Introduction

Oesophageal adenocarcinoma (OAC) is an aggressive inflammation driven, obesity associated cancer, with dismal 5-year survival rates of <20%. Patients face poor treatment response rates of <30% and urgently require new therapeutic options. Our group have previously shown natural killer (NK) cell viability and function is altered in omentum and liver of OAC patients. We have shown that the chemokine fractalkine drives cytotoxic T lymphocytes to omentum and mediates phenotypic alterations in these patients. We propose fractalkine governs erroneous NK cell migration to this tissue. This study aims to elucidate the role of fractalkine in NK cell migration and function in OAC. We propose targeting this pathway may prevent their depletion in omentum and facilitate harnessing their full therapeutic potential.

Methods

Total and CX3CR1+ NK cells were quantified in OAC patient blood, omentum and tumour by flow cytometry. Blood-derived NK cells were treated with 80µM of fractalkine receptor CX3CR1 antagonist (AZD8798) and their chemotaxis towards adipose tissue conditioned media (ACM) and tumour conditioned media (TCM) was measured using a transwell system. Non-cancer control NK cells were treated with 30ng/ml recombinant fractalkine and their surface CX3CR1, CD27 and CD69 expression and intracellular CD107a, IL-10, TNF-α and IFN-γ expression was measured by flow cytometry. NK cell cytotoxicity against K562 cells was measured by flow cytometry.

Results

Our data show that CX3CR1+ NK cell frequencies are diminished in OAC patient omentum (p<0.0001) and tumour (p<0.0001), compared to the circulation

and that intratumoural NK cell frequencies decline as visceral obesity increases in OAC patients ($r=-0.73$). Interestingly, CX3CR1 antagonism significantly reduces NK cell migration toward ACM but not TCM ($p=0.0431$). Treatment with fractalkine significantly reduces the expression of CX3CR1 on NK cells ($p=0.0271$). Conversely, it increases the expression of CD27 ($p=0.0401$), CD69 ($p=0.0008$), IL-10 ($p=0.0363$), TNF- α ($p=0.0194$) and IFN- γ ($p=0.0441$) by NK cells. NK cell cytotoxic ability was not dampened following treatment with fractalkine.

Discussion

CX3CR1 antagonism may offer a means of reducing fractalkine-governed NK cell migration to omentum in these patients. Fractalkine has non-chemotactic effects on NK cells, similar to that of CD8+ T cells where it modulates alterations in the phenotype and function of NK cells. Further work is needed to elucidate the full biological effects of this chemokine on NK cell phenotype and function in OAC.

SHORT TALK 121

Impact of NKC locus gene polymorphisms on natural killer cell function and outcome of immunotherapy in acute myeloid leukemia

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The NK complex (NKC) harbors multiple genes that are central to the regulation of NK cell functions, such as KLRK1 (encoding the activating receptor, NKG2D) and KLRC1 (encoding the inhibitory receptor, NKG2A). Previous reports suggest that high NK cell cytotoxicity is associated with lower cancer incidence, and that this in part is dependent on specific NKC haplotypes. There are several SNPs described in the NKC locus with reported impact on NK cell function. The majority of those are in the vicinity of the KLRK1 gene, except for one, which is in the promoter region of the KLRC1 gene. We recently described a pivotal role of NKG2A in AML patients after IL-2-based immunotherapy and this steered us to hypothesize that NK cell cytotoxicity may not only be associated with gene variants of NKG2D but also NKG2A. To address the effect of NKG2D variants on NK cell cytotoxicity, we used CRISPR to engineer K562 cells to create a triple-KO cell line that was killed in a highly NKG2D-dependent fashion. Using this tKO model, NK cells from NKG2D G/x individuals displayed only modestly higher degranulation compared to CC subjects. Moreover, NK subset analyses revealed that the superior degranulation response in G/x was largely related to the presence of a larger, highly responsive NKG2A+ subset, suggesting a role for NKG2A. Next,

we investigated biological and clinical consequences of NKG2A rs1983526. Interestingly, carriers of NKG2A GG genotype possessed significantly fewer NKG2A-KIR+ cells in comparison to NKG2A C/x patients. Additionally, AML patients with NKG2A GG had superior outcome after HDC/IL-2 immunotherapy. After stratifying patients for the HLA-B rs1050458, which dictates the strength of NKG2A-mediated NK cell education, we observed that NKG2A GG identified a subset of HLA-B-21 TT individuals with a favorable outcome. Taken together, our data suggest that previous findings associating NKC locus SNPs with increased NK cell function may not necessarily be driven by effects on NKG2D but rather be related to a linked SNP in the NKG2A gene. Furthermore, our study highlights the role of NKG2A+ NK cells in AML immunotherapy.

Session IV: ILCs and NK Cells Functions II

SHORT TALK 122

Investigating the metabolic requirements of cytokine induced natural killer cell training & the impact of obesity

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Natural killer (NK) cells are a population of innate immune cells which can rapidly kill cancer cells and produce cytokines such as interferon gamma (IFN-gamma). A key feature of NK cells is their ability to respond without prior sensitisation, however it is now well established that NK cells can possess memory-like features. After activation with cytokines, NK cells demonstrate enhanced effector functions upon restimulation days or weeks later. This demonstrates that NK cells may be “trained” to be more effective killers and harnessed as more potent cancer immunotherapy agents. We have previously demonstrated that cellular metabolism is essential for NK cell responses, with NK cells upregulating both glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation upon cytokine stimulation. Limiting NK cell metabolism results in

reduced cytotoxicity and cytokine production. We have also demonstrated that defective NK cell responses in obesity are linked to defective cellular metabolism. In the current study we investigated if cellular metabolism is required during the initial period of NK cell cytokine training, and if NK cells from people with obesity (PWO) can be effectively trained. We show that increased flux through glycolysis and OXPHOS during the initial cytokine activation period is essential for NK cell training, as is the metabolic signalling factor Srebp. We show that NK cells from PWO, which are metabolically defective, display impaired NK cell training, which may have implications for immunotherapy in this particularly vulnerable group.

SHORT TALK 123

Metabolic Differences on NK-92 cells expressing distinctive cytotoxic profiles from varying culturing process parameters

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Natural killer (NK) cell allogeneic immunotherapy is a promising treatment for cancer related malignancies. However, challenges persist when their manufacturing is automatized to generate sufficient, highly functional cells. NK cells' functionality is generally studied from the perspective of phenotype profiling, but that provides incomplete information about the dynamic conditions that drive the cells to express a specific effector profile. Furthermore, there is a growing body of evidence on cell metabolism being integral to NK cell functionality development, but their metabolic requirements have not been studied enough in detail, even less on its interdependence with culturing process parameters. In this study, we investigated the carbon and amino acid metabolism of NK-92 cells under different process parameters to understand and optimize their expansion

in-vitro, while searching for metabolic traits that could be useful as predictors for growth and functionality.

NK-92 cells were expanded in the presence of interleukin-2 and their functionality was determined by a cytotoxicity assay. Their activity was examined in the presence of low and normal oxygen tension, normal and elevated temperature, a range of shaking conditions (orbital shaker) and serum concentrations. We analyzed if a signature functionality/growth profile, triggered by changes in process parameters, could be correlated with different metabolite uptake and production rates throughout the 8-day culturing period. Hypoxia significantly reduced NK functionality while serum concentration caused differences in cytotoxicity. Increase in shear stress resulted in higher proliferation without

influencing NK cell functionality. Hyperthermia had no influence on functionality or growth. The results showed that the rate of NK-92 growth and uptake of certain amino acids were significantly higher for cells showing high cytotoxicity, cultured under normoxic conditions. Amino acid metabolic profile was found to be related to serum concentration: cells that were passaged sequentially into lower serum concentration showed an increase in nutrient uptake, with a maximum at 5% serum. This correlated with serum concentration, growth and functionality differences between cultures. However, variability was observed in the uptake of serine, tyrosine, leucine and

the production of alanine as well as with cytotoxicity. The data showed that there is a metabolic pattern for proliferating NK-92 cells with similar functionality but different growth patterns, which can contribute to the design of tailored medium for expansion. Additionally, the kinetic parameters found to describe nutrient usage into proliferation or functionality development will be useful to establish mechanistic models able to follow and predict optimal lymphocyte expansion.

SHORT TALK 124

The Role of Granzymes in NK Cell Cytotoxicity

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Granzymes (Grz) play an important role in NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity. While the cytotoxic activity of GrzB is well established, the contribution of the other human granzymes is much less studied. Here we use fluorescent localization reporters to detect the activity of Grz A, B, H, K, and M inside tumor target cells during NK cell-mediated killing by live cell imaging. For the NK92 cell line we could show that these NK cells exclusively use GrzB-mediated killing. However, while GrzB dominated most killing events of freshly isolated or activated human NK cells, we also detected the activity of other granzymes. While we did not detect any GrzH activity during NK cell-mediated killing events, GrzK initiated target cell apoptosis was observed for freshly isolated NK cells. Additionally, we found individual killing events of activated and freshly isolated NK cells where GrzA or GrzM activity was dominant. We also analyzed the Grz content of human NK cells by flow cytometry and found differential expression of the different granzymes in subpopulations of NK cells. Interestingly, the kinetics of granzyme depletion during target cell killing were similar for GrzA, B, and M, whereas we did not detect any depletion of GrzH, consistent with the absence of GrzH activity in target cells. However, GrzB levels recovered much faster compared to the other granzymes, demonstrating differential regulation of the granzymes. The reporter specificity was confirmed by CRISPR/Cas9 granzyme KO's which further gave us insights into alternative granzyme-mediated NK cell cytotoxicity. Furthermore, we analyzed the cytotoxic

efficacy of other granzymes compared to GrzB by Chromium-release assay and xCELLigence experiments but also the sensitivity of different target cells was tested. Here we observed a better efficacy for GrzB compared to GrzA, and an almost extinguished cytotoxicity when both were absent. These findings were comparable for the cell lines HeLa and 721.221, while Jurkat cells seem to be less sensitive to these two granzymes.

Currently, we are investigating the surface receptor phenotype of NK cell subpopulations with differential granzyme expression patterns to isolate and better characterize their functional activity.

SHORT TALK 125

Characterization of a panel of immortalized Natural Killer cell lines expressing allelic variants for FCGR3A

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Several allelic variants of the FCGR3A gene exist, where the high-affinity single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) V158F associates with the effectiveness of monoclonal antibody therapy. As to SNP L48H/R, H exhibits stronger binding to IgG1, IgG3, and IgG2 than R. The NK92 cell line resembles activated natural killer (NK) cells but lacks the expression of CD16 (FCGR3A).

AIM. To obtain a panel of NK92 cell lines expressing CD16 with the most common combinations of the SNPs L48H/R and V158F; and to test for differences in antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC).

METHODS. The different expression vectors were obtained by cloning FCGR3A into pVITRO and site-directed mutagenesis. NK92 cells were transfected by electroporation followed by geneticin selection. The CD16 expression was analysed by flow cytometry using three different anti-CD16 monoclonal antibody clones,

and ADCC tested by non-radioactive TDA release assays using anti-CD20 antibody and CD20-expressing Daudi cells as targets.

RESULTS. We generated and characterized FCGR3A combinations of SNPs on NK92 cell lines capable of ADCC. The NK92 transfectants exhibited no differences in terms of lytic activity triggered by anti-CD20 antibody engagement by CD16, regardless of the genetic variants involved. Albeit, dose-response curves showed that ADCC depended on anti-CD20 concentrations present in the assay.

CONCLUSIONS. We developed a tool for future ADCC studies. The four NK92 transfectants, accounting for more than 70% of the genotypes present in the population, showed no differences in ADCC.

SHORT TALK 126

Improving NK cell effector functions and manufacturing by EOMES and T-bet overexpression

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Natural killer (NK) cells are immune cells able to kill a wide variety of tumors. Glycostem's platform can generate large numbers of highly activated NK cells (oNKord®) from umbilical cord blood (UCB) CD34+ progenitors for adoptive immunotherapy applications. Nevertheless, some tumors display high resistance to oNKord® cell killing mechanisms. Antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity (ADCC) is a prominent killing mechanism mediated by the interaction of CD16 receptor with the Fc domain of human IgG1 antibodies. The oNKord® cells are almost devoid of CD16 expression and therefore ADCC cannot be mediated to clinically relevant extents against refractory tumors. Recent studies reported that overexpression of EOMES and T-bet, two paramount

transcription factors regulating the NK cell maturation pathways, is an indirect way of increasing CD16 expression in NK cells derived from UCB CD34+ hematopoietic stem cells, as well as significantly speeding up CD34+ differentiation into NK cells. However, overexpression was achieved by retroviral transduction and retrovirally transduced cells face tighter regulatory approval in the clinic than lentiviruses. On the other end, optimal lentiviral transduction on CD34+ HSCs is notoriously more difficult to achieve than retroviruses, especially with large constructs. We report how pharmaceutical applicable reprogramming of oNKord® culture by overexpression of EOMES and T-bet in UCB CD34+ HSCs can increase CD16 expression and reduce oNKord manufacturing times.

SHORT TALK 127

Adipokines' function in obesity-induced NK cell dysregulationGaitan Fabrice Njiomegnie¹, Scott A. Read¹, Ratna Wijaya¹, Jacob George¹, Golo Ahlenstiel¹¹Western Sydney University/ Westmead Institute for medical research; 19981156@student.westernsydney.edu.au

Obesity is defined as an excess accumulation of body fat that can significantly impair wellbeing. This condition has reached epidemic levels globally, with over 67% of adult Australians considered overweight (i.e., >12.5 million adults), and 20% clinically obese. Obesity presents with a multitude of comorbidities, contributing to the global burden of chronic diseases such as type 2 diabetes, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), and cardiovascular disorders. While many studies have addressed the low grade inflammation associated with obesity, there is a significant gap on how immune cell phenotype changes, both in circulation and in adipose/hepatic tissues. We aim to understand how obesity dysregulated adipokines such as adiponectin, leptin, chemerin and omentin alter natural killer (NK) cell phenotype. Defining NK cell dysregulation in obesity may help identify new therapeutic targets to reduce mortality associated with obesity and improve quality of life.

Our study utilises a cross-sectional cohort of patients with biopsy-proven NAFLD (N=100), stratified based on diabetes and severity of obesity. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from 10 morbidly obese patients (class II & III) and healthy controls were (1) phenotyped for adipokine receptor expression, and (2) assessed for cytotoxic and proliferative activity against target cells and in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines, respectively.

Our results suggest that obesity dysregulated adipokines such as adiponectin and chemerin play an important role in the activity of NK cells and warrant further study. Understanding the pro- and anti-inflammatory effects of key adipokines will enable targeted adipokine inhibition or supplementation based on patient-specific adipokine dysregulation.

SHORT TALK 128

TRAIL Engagement Induces Granule Exocytosis and Facilitates Degranulation of NK Cells Recognizing HIV-infected Target CellsJohannes Höfle¹, Timo Trenkner¹, Nadja Kleist¹, Vera Schwane¹, Sarah Vollmers¹, Annika Niehrs¹, Pia Fittje¹, Van Hung Huynh-Tran², Jürgen Sauter³, Alexander H. Schmidt³, Sven Peine⁴, Laura Richert², Marcus Altfeld¹, Christian Körner¹

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Background: NK cells utilize a large number of receptors to screen their cellular environment for potential threats. In a broader research approach, we sought to identify novel receptors that enable NK cells to recognize HIV-1-infected CD4+ T cells. Using a combination of comprehensive immunoprofiling of >300 surface antigens and a CD107a NK-cell degranulation assay, we identified multiple receptors that were associated with increased degranulation on NK cells after exposure to infected cells, including TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL). TRAIL exerts receptor-mediated cytotoxicity, inducing apoptosis through engagement of death receptors (DR4/5) on target cells. However, TRAIL has not been linked to granule-mediated cytotoxicity so far. Therefore, we further investigated the role of TRAIL

in degranulation.

Methods: Primary human NK cells and CD4+ T cells were enriched from healthy donors. Co-cultures of NK cells with autologous HIV-1-infected CD4 T cells or 721.221 cells were used to trigger NK cell degranulation. NK-cell degranulation and TRAIL expression were simultaneously assessed using flow cytometry. Degranulation was defined by surface expression of CD107a. In addition, we monitored CD107a expression in the presence of plate-coated anti-TRAIL or DR4 protein (TRAIL receptor 1). Finally, we blocked TRAIL through soluble anti-TRAIL and determined its effect on degranulation in the presence of 721.221 target cells.

Results: After exposure to HIV-I-infected cells, CD107a+ NK cells showed increased TRAIL expression (MFI & relative frequency) as compared to their non-responsive counterparts (n=19, p<0.01 both MFI and %). Subsequent experiments (n=13) indicated that TRAIL was neither significantly upregulated during NK-cell degranulation nor a surrogate marker for NK-cell subsets with higher baseline activity against HIV-I-infected cells. Furthermore, HIV-I-infected cells exhibited elevated expression of the TRAIL receptors, DR4 and DR5. Finally, engagement of TRAIL through plate-coated anti-TRAIL directly triggered degranulation of NK cells

(n=12, p<0.01). Similar results were obtained in the presence of plate-bound DR4 protein (n=6, p<0.05). In further support, blockade of TRAIL interaction by soluble anti-TRAIL significantly decreased NK-cell degranulation after exposure to 721.221 cells (n=10, p<0.01).

Discussion: Our results indicate that direct engagement of TRAIL induces degranulation of NK cells and facilitates NK-cell degranulation against HIV-I-infected cells. This mechanism attributes a new function for TRAIL in addition to its well-known role in receptor-mediated cytotoxicity.

Session V: NK Cells and Cancer II

SHORT TALK 129

Increased circulating TGF- β 1 is associated with impairment in NK cell effector functions in metastatic melanoma patients

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Background: Transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) plays a complex role in carcinogenesis. It represents one of the Main immunosuppressive cytokines produced by various cells in tumor microenvironment, including melanoma.

Aim: In this study we analyzed the level of circulating TGF- β 1 in metastatic melanoma (MM) patients compared to healthy controls (HC), as well as the association between this cytokine and NK cell effector functions and receptors expression in MM patients.

Material and methods: In 20 MM patients and 20 HC we analyzed functional and phenotypic characteristics of NK cells by Flow cytometry, gene expression of TGF- β 1 in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) by qPCR and serum level of circulating TGF- β 1 by ELISA.

Results: MM patients compared to HC not only had significantly higher level of TGF- β 1 gene in PBMC, but also had increased percentage of CD14+HLA-DR- myeloid derived suppressor cells and high mean fluorescence intensity of FoxP3 in CD4+CD25+ regulatory T cells. Furthermore, MM patients had significantly higher serum level of free TGF- β 1 compared to HC, especially patients with metastasis into the central nervous system (subclass M1d) compared to patients in subclasses M1a+M1b and subclass M1c. In MM patients

there was negative correlation between serum level of TGF- β 1 and the NK cell expression of CD107a, perforin, IFN- γ , NKG2D, NKp46.

Conclusions: In this study we show in MM patients the association of high level of TGF- β 1 with NK cell inhibition that represents the main mechanism of tumor immune evasion. Targeting TGF- β may represent an important cancer treatment for improving antitumor immunity.

SHORT TALK 130

PARP inhibitors Olaparib and AG-14361 render otherwise resistant breast and ovarian cancers sensitive towards NK cell mediated killing.

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NK cells can rapidly eliminate cancer cells and represent attractive effectors for adoptive cancer immunotherapy. Nevertheless, some cancers have developed mechanisms in order to escape NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity. Strategies to improve NK cell potency towards resistant cancers are highly demanded in order to fully harness the therapeutic potential of NK cells. While of NK cells by chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-mediated cytotoxicity towards tumor associated antigens expressed on has shown potential in otherwise resistant cancers, the combination with check point inhibitors or molecules that upregulate NK cell-activating ligands is not well examined.

We were recently able to show that retargeting by CAR in NK cells provide the necessary signals, leading to granule polarization and thereby overcoming tumor cell resistance (Eitler et al. JITC 2021). We now used high throughput IncuCyte live-cell imaging system to analyze the impact of checkpoint inhibition and the NK cell activating ligand upregulator (PARP inhibitor) Olaparib and AG-14361 in the context of natural and CAR-mediated cytotoxicity. The ErbB2+ breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-453 and the ovarian carcinoma cell line SKOV-3, both of which resistant to parental NK-92 cells, were exposed to combinations of clinically-approved checkpoint inhibitors Nivolumab (anti-PD-1), Avelumab (anti-PD-L1), Ipilimumab (anti-CTLA-4) and PARP

inhibitors. The combinations were examined with regard to their effect on NK cell mediated killing by NK-92 cells and its anti-ErbB2 CAR-redirected version (NK-92/5.28z). Interestingly, although both, the checkpoint receptor PD-1 and its ligand PD-L1 on cancer cells were upregulated on NK cells and cancer cells, respectively, blocking with Nivolumab or Avelumab did not improve the cytotoxicity of NK-92 or CAR-NK-92 towards MDA-MB-453 or to SKOV-3. In contrast, coincubation with PARP inhibitors improved natural killing towards SKOV-3 and MDA-MB-453 cancer cells compared to single-treated controls. which we further confirmed in 3D spheroid culture system. Flow cytometric analysis indicates that treatment with PARP inhibitors causes upregulation of the NK cell activation ligands MICA/B, CD112 or CD115 on cancer cells, which may result in sensitization of cancer cells towards NK-92.

Taken together, we have shown that PARP inhibitors directly improve the NK cell potency towards otherwise resistant breast and ovarian cancers by upregulation of activating signals and offers an attractive approach to better harness the patients NK cell response and/or in combination with adoptive NK cell based cancer therapies.

SHORT TALK 131

Oncogenic potential of mutant STAT5B in natural killer cells

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The signal transducer and activator of transcription 5B (STAT5B) regulates development, survival and function of innate(-like) lymphocytes. The STAT5B gain-of-function

mutation N642H is associated with aggressive forms of CD56+ T (NKT) and NK cell lymphomas/leukemias. A mouse model expressing human STAT5BN642H

under the Vav1 promoter develops severe CD8⁺ T cell malignancies. In the absence of classical T cells, Vav1-driven STAT5B-N642H promotes aggressive innate-like NKT cell leukemia, resembling CD56⁺ T-cell large granular lymphocyte (T-LGL) leukemia. We aim to investigate whether STAT5B-N642H also acts as an oncogenic driver in NK cells and establish an NK cell leukemia model to enable the development of treatment options for currently untreatable NK cell malignancies. While Vav1-driven STAT5B-N642H caused a temporary expansion of NK cells, no NK cell disease was observed in this model. To avoid competition with more potently transformed cell types, we generated a novel mouse model in which STAT5B-N642H expression is restricted to the NK (NKp46-positive) cell lineage. These mice show increased NK cell numbers, while disease symptoms have not yet been detected up to an age of 6 months. Furthermore, STAT5B-N642H expressing NK cells cultured with high-dose IL-2 display a decreased

expansion capacity, associated with a functional impairment. These data suggest that STAT5B-N642H on its own might not be able to transform NK cells, in contrast to other cell types. Ageing experiments will be continued to investigate an oncogenic potential of mutant STAT5B in NK cells at a later timepoint. Additionally, we will continue to explore the underlying mechanisms of the detrimental role of hyperactive STAT5B signaling on NK cell function. This knowledge will contribute to a better understanding of the complex regulation of NK cell activities that is valuable as NK cells are being pursued as immunotherapeutic tools.

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SHORT TALK 132

Ex vivo expanded NK cells show potent anti-tumour activity against melanoma

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Current therapies for metastatic melanoma fail to cure patients since they develop resistance to the treatments. In addition, immune infiltrates are often found in melanoma, but inactive due to the immunosuppressive environment. Taken this together, it makes melanoma a good target candidate for adoptive cell therapies. We investigated whether melanoma is a good target for our stem cell ex vivo generated Natural Killer (NK) cell product GTA002 and explored the killing mechanisms against melanoma.

CD34⁺ cells were isolated from umbilical cord blood, expanded and differentiated into active NK cells *in vitro*. Cytotoxic capacity of the NK cells from different donors were determined against 9 different human melanoma cell lines during a 5-hour and a 20-hour co-culture assay with an E:T ratio of 1:1. In parallel, degranulation together with intracellular levels of perforin and Granzyme B, and the pro-inflammatory cytokines IFN γ and TNF α were measured in the 5-hour co-culture using flow cytometry.

Cytotoxic responses were observed towards all 9 melanoma cell lines in a 5-hour co-culture, with varying killing susceptibility ranging from 7.8% to 40.2% killing, depending on the melanoma cell line. The 20-hour co-culture assay showed only a small increase in killing, suggesting that the NK cells exert quick cytotoxic response in the first hours. Intracellular levels of perforin

and granzyme B in NK cells were decreased already after 5 hours of co-culture with the melanoma cell lines compared to no-target controls, indicating release of lytic granules quickly after target engagement.

Increased levels of IFN γ and TNF α were observed in NK cells after co-culture to varying degrees depending on the melanoma cell line. Interestingly, the relative cytotoxic performance of an individual NK cell donor was consistent throughout the melanoma target cell panel. However, we still observed differences in killing between melanoma cell lines, suggesting that this could be attributed to different expression profiles of NK cell receptor ligands on the target cells. Therefore, detailed phenotypic profiling for both NK cell activating and inhibitory receptors as well as for ligands expressed on the melanomas is currently on-going.

Our data show that GTA002 NK cells exert efficient anti-tumour activity against melanoma cell lines *in vitro*. In order to better understand the differences in susceptibility to NK cell mediated killing between the different melanoma cell lines, we will further investigate the involvement of different killing mechanisms taking into account the contribution of the individual ligand expression profile of melanomas to NK cell activation.

SHORT TALK 133

Non-viral Sleeping Beauty transposon engineered CD19-CAR-NK cells show a safe genomic integration profile and high antileukemic efficiency

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Natural Killer (NK) cells are known for their high intrinsic cytotoxic capacity. Recently, we showed that virally transduced NK cells equipped with a synthetic chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) targeting CD19 induced enhanced killing of acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) cells. Here, we demonstrate that primary NK cells can be engineered through non-viral Sleeping Beauty (SB) transposon/transposase system to stably express CD19-CAR. SB transposons vectorized as minicircles (MC), which encode either a Venus fluorescent protein or a CD19-CAR, were introduced in combination with the hyperactive SB100X transposase into primary NK cells via electroporation (EP). Stable gene delivery and biological activity were monitored by flow cytometry and cytotoxicity of CD19-CAR NK cells against CD19-positive ALL cell lines.

Applying a protocol optimized with respect to EP pulses, time points and plasmid ratios, primary NK cells showed long-lasting Venus expression (up to 50%) upon SB-mediated gene delivery with similar viability as non-treated (NT) NK cells during ex-vivo expansion using IL-15. Likewise, SB transposon-engineered CD19-CAR NK cells displayed high viability and long-lasting transgene expression up to 40% over one month.

CD19-CAR-NK cells generated with the SB platform demonstrated significantly higher cytotoxicity compared to NT NK cells against the CD19-positive ALL cell lines

SUP-B15 and NALM6. SUP-B15 tumor cell lysis was significantly enhanced after 4 hours of co-culture with CD19-CAR NK cells than with NT NK cells in a broad range of effector to target (E:T) ratios: E:T-20:1 86% vs 20%; E:T-10:1 74% vs 20%; E:T-5:1 54% vs 17%; E:T-1:1 36% vs 18%. This enhanced tumor killing capacity was thereby comparable to that of lentivirally engineered CD19-CAR NK cells.

Importantly, SB100X-generated CD19-CAR NK cells showed a significantly more random genomic integration profile than lentivirally transduced CD19-CAR NK cells, with a significantly higher frequency of vector integration into genomic safe harbors (GSH). These are defined as regions of human chromosomes simultaneously satisfying the following five criteria: not ultraconserved, >300 kb away from miRNA genes, >50kb away from transcriptional start sites (TSS), >300kb away from genes involved in cancer and outside transcription units. Taken together, our data establish the Sleeping Beauty transposon system as an innovative and promising gene therapy approach for non-viral engineering of safe, highly functional and relatively cost-efficient CAR-NK cells that may not only be suitable for ALL therapy but also for a broad range of other applications in cancer therapy.

SHORT TALK 134

Emergence of polyfunctional ST2+ NK cells with antitumor properties following IL-33 Activation

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Natural Killer (NK) cells have evolved into a spectrum of effector subsets in terms of functions and responsiveness to activating stimuli to ensure complementary roles in immune responses. These innate lymphocytes,

harbor direct cytotoxic and support functions, notably through the secretion of cytokines and chemokines, thus regulating antigen-presenting cells (APC) and the adaptive responses of T cells. In a vast majority of cancers, NK-mediated immunosurveillance plays a major role from early stages of oncogenesis to the prevention of metastasis dissemination. NK cell activation relies on the integration of multiple extrinsic signals, however, these cells get progressively dysfunctional in cancer contexts and the mechanisms allowing to restore their anti-tumor functions still need to be deepened. Cytokines are essential for the regulation of NK cells' differentiation, survival, and activation but, to date, research works mainly focused on three of them, IL-12/IL-15/IL-18, highlighting the necessity to identify other NK cell regulators. In this project, we investigated the contribution of the IL-33 alarmin in NK cell activation from healthy donor *in vitro* and in the context of breast cancer. First, we defined culture conditions with exogenous cytokines allowing to induce IL33R/ST2 expression either specifically on different NK cell subsets or on a majority of NK cells that acquire the ability to strongly respond to IL-33. We also highlighted the importance of dendritic cells-

derived IL-12 in ST2 induction during NK/APC crosstalk. Transcriptomic analysis revealed a unique transcriptional program of IL-12-induced ST2+ NK cells with effector and proliferative abilities, defining a new intermediate differentiation state between canonical CD56bright and CD56dim NK. Interestingly, ST2+ NK cells are of interest in tumor context since they were detected in tumor and blood from cancer patients, and were able to produce IFN- γ in response to IL-33. Consistently, injection of IL-33 and IL-12 in a mammary tumor mouse model resulted in decreased tumor formation, improved survival, and induced IFN- γ secretion, through NK cells. Furthermore, several solid tumors with an IL33hi-NKhi score showed increased patient survival. Thus, our work identifies IL-33 as a new potent NK cell activator and describes ST2+ NK cells as a polyfunctional/hyperresponsive population. We propose IL-33 as an actor involved in NK-cell mediated breast cancer immunosurveillance that might be used to reverse intratumor NK cell dysfunctionality, paving the way to a refinement of NK-centered cancer therapies.

SHORT TALK 135

Complement 5a Receptor 2 (C5aR2) expression regulates NKp46 levels and influences formation of pulmonary metastases

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The second receptor for the complement component and anaphylatoxin C5a was initially considered a decoy receptor. This view has been challenged by findings demonstrating that C5aR2 activation induces pro- and anti-inflammatory functions, depending on the context. However, the functional properties of C5aR2 remain enigmatic. We reported the expression of C5aR2 on murine natural killer cells, surprisingly without the usual co-expression of C5aR1. We observed that the systemic absence of C5aR2 leads to a strongly increased NKp46 expression in NK cells. This newly found NKp46 overexpression raises the proposition that systemic C5aR2 expression negatively regulates NKp46 surface levels and might therefore be involved in modulating NK cell cytotoxic activity, possibly relevant for the response towards metastatic tumors. We approached the analysis of the role of C5aR2 in NK cell responses towards metastases by investigating the effects of a general as well as a NK cell-specific lack of C5aR2 in a NK cell-dependent murine pulmonary metastases model. Due to the elevated NKp46 expression in systemic C5aR2-deficient mice, the absence of C5aR2 might influence the outcome of metastatic cancer, where NK cell cytotoxicity is pivotal.

B16-F10 murine melanoma cells were injected intravenously into wild type, systemically and NK cell-specific C5aR2-deficient C57BL/6 mice through the tail vein. The disease progress, according to a general disease score, was monitored daily. On day 7, 14 or 21 post injection mice were sacrificed, and macroscopically observable surface metastatic foci were enumerated. NKp46 expression was assessed by flow cytometry.

Our investigations revealed that systemically C5aR2-deficient mice developed fewer metastatic foci on the lung surface compared to their wild type counterparts after 7, 14 and 21 days post tumor cell injection. Consistently, C5aR2-deficient mice featured a lower disease score and a better overall survival over a time period of 21 days. Surprisingly, NK cell-specific C5aR2-deficient mice did not show a reduced tumor burden, or a milder disease progress compared to wild type controls. In accordance with these findings, our experiments show for NK cell-specific C5aR2-deficient mice that NKp46 levels are similar to those in wild type mice.

Our findings demonstrate for the first time the relevance

of systemic C5aR2 expression in the context of NKp46 regulation and thus, metastatic cancer. We hypothesize that systemic C5aR2 expression has a negative effect on the regulation of NKp46 surface levels during NK cell

development. Therefore, C5aR2 could prove a useful target to augment NKp46-dependent NK cell cytotoxicity, ultimately preventing metastases formation.

Session VI: NK and ILC Development and Regulation

SHORT TALK 136

A comprehensive platform for the faithful generation of human innate lymphoid cell lineages from CD34+ hematopoietic progenitors

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Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) are critical effectors of innate immunity, particularly at mucosal surfaces. Besides fetal lymphoid tissue inducer (LTi) cells, post-natal ILCs can be classified into ILC1, ILC2, ILC3, and NK cells. While *in vitro* generation of T helper lineages has expanded our understanding of developmental requirements, ILC engenderment has not been systematically explored, and previous investigations relied on the analysis of few markers or cytokines, which are suboptimal to assign lineage identity. Here, we present a comprehensive

platform which allows the reliable generation of human ILC lineages from CD34+ progenitors derived from cord blood and bone marrow. Validation by global and single cell transcriptome analysis exposes the power and the limitations of the system in engendering mature and functional ILCs which recapitulate their *ex vivo* counterparts. These data represent a resource to aid in clarifying ILC biology and differentiation.

SHORT TALK 137

Regulation of Fra-2 is essential for correct Natural Killer Cell development and function

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Systemic Sclerosis is a chronic autoimmune disease characterized by inflammation and tissue remodeling. Increased expression of the AP-1 transcription factor Fra-2 and alteration of Natural Killer (NK) cell function and receptor expression has been reported in these patients. In mice ectopic overexpression of Fra-2 (transgenic (TG)) leads to a systemic sclerosis phenotype, strongly affecting the skin and lung. In Fra-2 TG mice, a time dependent development of pulmonary fibrosis, vascular remodeling, and recruitment of inflammatory cells to the lungs was

observed, as characterized by macrophage polarization, and increased T cells and eosinophils. However, a reduced number of NK cells was already observed before the first signs of lung fibrosis and although the role of several immune cells such as macrophages, B and T lymphocytes has been investigated, the contribution of NK cells to disease pathogenesis remains elusive. The focus of this study was to determine the role of Fra-2 in development and function of NK cells and their role in SSc.

Decreased NK numbers were also observed in the blood, spleen, and liver of Fra-2 TG mice, suggesting a defect in NK cell development. Flow Cytometry analysis of murine bone marrow showed significantly decreased numbers of all NK-specific precursors in Fra2 TG mice, beginning at the stage of preNKP. To determine the role of Fra-2 in NK development, mixed bone marrow chimera experiments were performed. These showed that the defect caused by Fra-2 is cell intrinsic and not dependent on the environment. This finding was confirmed by *in vitro* differentiation, using isolated NK precursors, in which TG cells showed decreased differentiation capacity.

Furthermore, isolated mature NK cells from TG mice showed decreased maturity (assessed by surface marker

expression), proliferation (as shown by ki67 staining and cell counts), *in vitro* cytotoxicity and increased caspase activation (shown by intracellular FACS staining) compared to WT NK cells.

In Summary, our data demonstrates that regulation of Fra-2 is essential for correct NK cell development and function and suggest that NK cells may play an important role in the development of lung fibrosis in systemic sclerosis and restoration of NK could prevent the progression of the disease.

SHORT TALK 138

Deep characterisation of neonatal innate lymphoid subsets reveals a unique precursor able to generate NKG2A-KIR+ NK cells

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Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) have been described to be vital for innate immunity due to maintenance of tissue homeostasis and barrier functions. Despite the well described role of ILCs within tissues, phenotypical and functional analyses of circulating ILCs are rare. Since peripheral (PB) and neonatal blood (CB) ILCs are easily accessible compared to tissue ILCs, their thorough characterization is highly desirable in order to assess their usefulness for future cellular therapy. We have characterized CB ILCs by phenotypic, functional, and transcriptomic analyses. All three ILC subsets showed unique gene signatures as well as nine shared genes including ID3, CD28, SLAMF1, and CCR4. Unlike previously described tissue ILCs, CB ILCs showed a unique ID3/ID2 ratio > 1, which was similarly seen in CB CD4+ T cells, but not in PB ILCs, CB NK cells, tonsillar ILC3, PB T cells, or CB CD8+ T cells. Thus CB ILCs and CD4+ T cells might share a common developmental pathway, possibly within the thymus. In line with this theory, ILC1-like cells closely resembled T cells by expression of CD5, CD6, CD28, CCR4, CCR9, CCR7, TRAV, TRBV, and intracellular CD3 δ . Notably, CB ILC1-like cells (but not other ILCs) exhibited a significant decrease in frequency and total cell count during gestational ageing, which might point towards migration into tissues, e.g. secondary lymph nodes. When stimulated with specific cytokines, we did not observe effector functions such as IFN γ secretion suggesting that CB ILC1-like cells might constitute an immature precursor. Indeed, we identified

CB ILC1-like cells as a novel type of CD117- NK cell progenitor, which was able to differentiate on bulk and clonal level to NKG2A-KIR+ NK cells, representing an advanced grade of NK cell maturation. As CB ILC1-like cells are to our knowledge the first precursor able to efficiently differentiate into mature NKG2A-KIR+ NK cells, this finding may be interesting for future therapeutic applications. In this regard, we have established a novel *in vitro* platform based on human mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) that efficiently supports ILC and NK cell differentiation and enables GMP-compliant generation of mature NK cell subpopulations including NKG2A-KIR+ NK cells that might be useful for future therapeutic applications.

SHORT TALK 139**T-BET and EOMES accelerate and enhance functional differentiation of human NK cells by programming HPCs**

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T-bet and Eomes are key transcription factors in maturation, homeostasis and function of murine natural killer (NK) cells. In contrast to mice, the current knowledge on the role of T-BET and EOMES in human NK cells is rudimentary. Here, we ectopically expressed T-BET or EOMES in human hematopoietic progenitor cells (HPC). Transcriptome, chromatin accessibility and protein expression profiling revealed that T-BET or EOMES overexpression in HPC epigenetically represses hematopoietic stem cell quiescence and non-NK lineage differentiation genes, while activating an NK cell-specific transcriptome and thereby drastically accelerating NK cell differentiation. The effects of T-BET and EOMES on NK cell differentiation are largely overlapping, yet EOMES shows a superior role in early NK cell maturation and induces faster NK receptor and enhanced CD16 expression. In-depth analysis of NK cells differentiated

upon T-BET or EOMES overexpression shows that these cells undergo terminal maturation. Particularly T-BET controls transcription of terminal maturation markers and epigenetically controls strong induction of KIR expression. Finally, NK cells generated upon T-BET or EOMES overexpression display improved functionality, including increased IFN- γ production and killing, and especially EOMES overexpression NK cells have enhanced antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity. Altogether, these findings reveal novel insights on the regulatory role of T-BET and EOMES in human NK cell maturation and function, which is essential to further understand NK cell biology and to optimize adoptive NK cell therapies.

SHORT TALK 140**KLRG1+ILCp as a Putative Progenitor of IL-13-Producing ILC3 in the Human Liver**

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Background: Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) have been shown to fundamentally modulate homeostasis and inflammation in numerous tissues. While their plastic nature has been highlighted in multiple experimental studies, little is known about the dynamics of the intrahepatic ILC pool in the steady-state as well as in the course of chronic liver disease (CLD).

Material & Methods: Human liver ILCs (non-fibrotic (n=18), fibrotic/cirrhotic (n=14)) were characterized by

flow cytometry, bulk gene expression analysis (qPCR) as well as sc-3'RNA-Sequencing (10x Genomics, Inc.). Analysis was focused on their functional capacities as well as phenotypical differences in comparison to other compartments such as tonsils (n=8), colon mucosae (n=14) and peripheral blood (n=32). Functional experiments also included the impact of ILC-derived cytokines on human hepatic stellate cells (HStCs). Furthermore, the effect of recombinant cytokines and metabolites on ILC plasticity was studied using an OP9-

DL4 stromal cell-based *in vitro* culture system.

Results: Unexpectedly, we found that intrahepatic CRTH2(-)CD117(+)NKp44(+/-) ILCs substantially contribute to IL-13-production by human liver ILCs. These cells appeared to be specifically enriched in the human liver, as only marginal numbers could be observed among tonsillar, colonic or peripheral blood ILCs. Moreover, increased frequencies of this cell type were found in fibrotic/cirrhotic livers compared to non-fibrotic controls, indicating a potential involvement in hepatic fibrogenesis.

In contrast to conventional ILC2, IL-13(+)CRTH2(-) (CD117(+)) ILCs displayed a distinct ILC3-specific expression signature and were also functionally distinct as they could not be induced by IL-33 and TSLP. Following up on recent reports, we could demonstrate that upon exposure to IL 1 β , IL-23, TGF β and the Ahr ligand FICZ, both ILC2 as well as KLRG1(+)CRTH2(-)

CD117(+) ILCs (K+ILCp) were able to transdifferentiate into IL13(+)CRTH2(-)CD117(+)NKp44(+) cells. However, detailed mRNA analysis of post-culture isolated cells revealed, that only K+ILCp acquired a gene expression signature similar to the one observed in intrahepatic IL-13+CRTH2-CD117+ cells. Of note, this putative progenitor subset was also found to be increased in the human liver when compared to other compartments, thereby further emphasizing its potential involvement in the tissue-specific emergence of IL-13+CRTH2-CD117+ liver ILCs.

Conclusion: In summary, our data indicate that the specific composition of the human intrahepatic ILC pool and the liver microenvironment give rise to formerly uncharacterized cell type of IL-13-producing ILC3-like cells, which appears to arise from transdifferentiation of KLRG1+ ILCp.

SHORT TALK 141

Toggling of NKG2A expression drives adaptive reprogramming and functional specialization of iPSC-derived CD19 CAR NK cells

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Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived natural killer (iNK) cells offer a promising platform for off-the-shelf immunotherapy against hematological malignancies. A unique benefit of iPSC-derived immune effector cells is the possibility to perform multiple precision editing steps at the single cell level to achieve a homogenous effector cell population tailored to target a desired cancer type and equipped with selected functional properties. These functional edits are superimposed on the innate reactivity of NK cells to stress ligands and MHC downregulation (missing self). The ability of NK cells to sense missing self is based on a functional calibration to self MHC during a process termed NK cell education, the latter being critically dependent on signaling through canonical inhibitory receptors, including CD94/NKG2A and killer cell immunoglobulin-like receptors (KIR). Whereas the differentiation of NK cells into mature effector cells from iPSCs has been well characterized, the role of natural variation in inhibitory receptor expression and NK cell

education remains poorly defined in iNK cells.

We monitored functional responses by a range of genetically engineered iPSC-derived NK cell lines, including iNK-CAR19 cells, against K562, K562.HLA-E and CD19+ Nalm-6 cells. Subset stratification showed that NKG2A+ iNK cells had superior functionality compared to NKG2A- iNK cells across all iNK cell lines tested. CRISPR knock out of b2microglobulin (b2m) in iNK cells revealed that the functional potency of NKG2A+ iNK cells was independent of NKG2A-HLA-E interactions in cis or trans during differentiation. NKG2A+ iNK cells expressed higher levels of Eomes, granzyme B, KIR and DNAM-1, suggesting a more differentiated phenotype that could explain the enhanced functional potency of this iNK cell subset. CRISPR-mediated ablation of NKG2A led to a reduced global functional responsiveness but was associated with increased levels of the activating receptor NKG2C. Interestingly, NKG2C+ iNK cells

showed functional specialization with increased IFN- γ production in response to receptor ligation, similar to conventional adaptive NK cells.

Our results shed light on the regulatory gene circuits and cellular programs that determine functional potential in iPSC-derived NK cells products. Specifically, our results

point to a crucial role for NKG2A-driven acquisition of a mature effector cell phenotype and highlight the need to consider subset diversity and receptor interactions in the design of iNK cell therapy strategies.

SHORT TALK 142

Ex vivo Expanded NK Cells and Their Immunometabolism

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Natural killer (NK) cells play an important role in innate immune responses. Upon cytokine and other receptors activation NK cells are able to directly kill cancer and pathogen-infected cells without previous sensitization. Therefore, NK cells have an excellent potential for immunotherapy, in spite of their low numbers (5-15%) among peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs). The increasing research aims to identify the approaches allowing the expansion of primary NK cells to large numbers suitable for adoptive transfer based immunotherapy. NK cell expansion requires multiple signals for survival, proliferation and activation. Furthermore, it is also known that NK cells differentiation and effector function are strongly affected by cellular metabolism. Activated NK cells have high demands for ATP molecules for energy consumption and nutrients for anabolic synthesis to cater for their effector functions. Glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) are two major metabolic pathways to provide energy for these cells.

Here we address several NK cells ex vivo expansion strategies comparing the effect of cytokines (IL-2, IL-15, IL-21) irradiated allogeneic PBMCs or monocytes on expansion, cytotoxicity and immunometabolism. Ex vivo exposure to cytokines IL-2 and IL-15 increases glycolysis and OXPHOS in NK cells to support their effector function. Our results also demonstrate that ex vivo expanded NK cells are phenotypically and functionally different comparing to freshly isolated NK cells. Furthermore, expanded NK cells exert increased cytotoxicity toward K562 and THP1 target cells through release of cytolytic proteins, such as perforin, granzymes, and produce pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IFN- γ and TNF- α .

These results are in line with our data from Seahorse bioanalyzer suggesting that increased glycolysis and OXPHOS support NK cell cytotoxicity and degranulation.

This study aims to improve knowledge of processes controlling the effector cytotoxic function of NK cells important for cell immunotherapy of haemato-oncological disorders.

SHORT TALK 143**Forecast the outcome of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation via the evaluation of NK cells functions and their differential expression of natural killer cells receptors in the donors**

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The established treatment of AML is extensive chemotherapy followed by allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. Successful HSCT depend mostly on the graft vs leukemia (GVL) effect which plays a major role in the eradication of residual leukemic cells. The main key players in GVL are the T- lymphocytes and natural killer (NK) cells of the donor-derived alloreactive immune cells which play a major role in the eradication of residual leukemic cells. Albeit, a significant number of the HSCT recipients develop side effects such as GVHD or relapse. Recently, a large body of controversial data has been accumulated on the contribution of natural killer (NK) cells to graft-versus-malignancy (GVL) effects following HSCT. Our pilot study showed that, failure to achieve remission in AML was associated with over expression of the inhibitory natural killer receptor NKG2A and down regulation of NK46 on NK cells of their donors. Therefore we initiated this study to further investigate the role of NK cells in the eradication of residual leukemia and whether we can predict HSCT outcome based on the differential expression of natural killer cells receptors (NCR) on the innate immune cells and their *in vitro* functions. Finally, this is the first study of its kind in closely genetic related population with a high consanguinity, predicting the outcome of HSCT based on NK cells cells functions.

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